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CLIMATE RESILIENT AND ENVIRONMENTALLY
SUSTAINABLE TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE,
WITH A FOCUS ON INLAND WATERWAYS

D8.2 RP Solution description, test results and impact assessment

**CRISTAL - Climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport
infrastructure, with a focus on inland waterways**

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable aims to present the tests of the CRISTAL technologies conducted on the French inland waterways. It covers three technologies developed by VNF, CEDRE (Data Collection & Exchange within the European Network), Fluv'IOTe, and the French smart buoys, as well as four technologies led by UNEW, Euromobilita, CERTH (SCMS, Synchronomodal corridor management system, Acoustic Emissions), and Fraunhofer (Digital twin).

Building on Deliverable 8.1, which outlined the testing context from both physical (the waterways) and stakeholder (actor-related challenges) perspectives, this report details the development process of the CEDRE technology, the functionalities of all seven technologies, the test results, the data collected and processed, and provides a critical assessment of the methodology used.

The deliverable highlights the interdependence of the tested technologies, emphasising that their combined use is necessary to meet the objectives of promoting modal shift and improving resilience.

To support this analysis, data were gathered through interviews and questionnaires with technology providers and VNF operational teams. It also draws on input from the living labs conducted by VNF with end users and technical departments, to evaluate the impacts of these technologies within the French context, specifically in relation to the KPIs defined in Deliverables D6.1 and D8.1.

The findings focus on how these technologies affect professional practices, and more broadly, on how they contribute to the modernisation of maintenance procedures, enhancement of modal shift, and increased resilience in inland waterway transport.

This deliverable is complemented by the tests conducted on the Polish and Italian pilots, the synthesis provided by Work Package 6, and dedicated deliverables offering deeper insights into specific technologies.

The analysis of technology readiness, field performance of various functionalities, and their impact on KPIs helps identify the most critical features needed to achieve the goals of modal shift and enhanced resilience.

Introduction

The main goal of the present handbook is to provide an overview of the tests realised in the French pilot.

The CRISTAL project aims to develop technological strategies to increase the modal share of inland waterway freight by 20%, improve its reliability by 80%, and maintain 50% operational capacity during extreme weather events. A set of innovative solutions is being co-developed and tested across three pilot sites, including one in France.

This deliverable follows Deliverable 8.1, which outlined the French inland waterways, their specific challenges, and stakeholder positioning. It presents the main functionalities of the seven technologies tested on the French pilot site, the data collection and processing methodology, and the test results.

The project leverages the potential of the Physical Internet and digitalization, and aims to design new decision support systems, such as a synchronized/multimodal corridor management system. Proposed solutions include the deployment of sensors and structural health monitoring technologies for infrastructure assessment, as well as the development of predictive models for navigation.

The tests conducted on the French pilot site are intended to raise the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the selected technologies up to level 7, contributing to the creation of a “future-proof,” climate-resilient infrastructure system.

Among the seven technologies tested on French rivers as part of the CRISTAL project, three were developed and tested by VNF’s internal teams:

- CEDRE technology, which standardizes and simplifies information systems regarding transported goods,
- Smart buoys, which transmit real-time navigation support data,
- Fluv’IOTe, an AI-powered system providing information on quay occupancy.

The four other technologies tested on the French river pilot were led by UNEW, Euromobilita, CERTH, and Fraunhofer: the SIR technology, the Corridor Management System, acoustic emission sensors, and digital twins.

The objective is to identify the innovative features of the solutions tested in the CRISTAL project, to assess their performance in real-life conditions, based on the results available at this stage, and to understand how they are received and adopted by inland waterway professionals, in order to support modal shift towards waterway transport and enhance the resilience of inland navigation.

Mapping CRISTAL outputs

The purpose of this section is to provide an overview of the alignment of the document to the formal deliverable & corresponding task descriptions included in the GA and thus help the deliverable owners and the reviewers to conclude on the level of achievement of the deliverable/task goals.

Table 1 Alignment of D8.2 contents to the corresponding GA deliverable & task(s) descriptions

CRISTAL GA Component Title	CRISTAL GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D 8.2, RP Solution description, test results and impact assessment	<i>D8.2 will include descriptions of electronic freight documentation (CEDRE), a tool to optimize loadings and IoT for the purposes of navigation facilitation and safety</i>	1 - 6	<i>Section 2 describes the solutions, including CEDRE, section 3 presents the test results, and section 4 the impact assessment.</i>
TASKS			
Task 8.1 Electronic freight documentation (CEDRE), a tool to optimize loadings	<i>Understand the needs of carriers, shippers and charterers, inventory of the technical solutions available, build a solution, reform the freight toll</i>	2.1, 3.1, 4.2, 4.3	<i>Description, test results, and impact assessment of CEDRE.</i>
Task 8.2 Use of IoT for the purpose of navigation facilitation and safety	<i>Experiments to test IoT devices</i>	2.2, 3.2, 4.2, 4.3	<i>Description, test results, and impact assessment of Fluv'IOTe.</i>
Task 8.3 Flood management on the Moselle river : use of smart buoys	<i>Description and test of buoys</i>	2.3, 3.3, 4.2, 4.3	<i>Description, test results, and impact assessment of smart buoys.</i>
Task 8.4 Tools for predictive infrastructure maintenance	<i>Test of SIR and use for predictive maintenance</i>	2.4, 3.4, 4.2, 4.3	<i>Description, test results, and impact assessment of SIR.</i>

Task 8.5 Corridor Management	<i>Test of SCMS</i>	2.5, 2.6, 2.7, 3.5, 3.6, 3.7, 4.2, 4.3	<i>Description, test results, and impact assessment of SCMS, Acoustic Emissions, and Digital Twin.</i>
Task 8.6 Governance	<i>Living labs</i>	4.2, 4.3	<i>Impact assessment through the living labs</i>

Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The present report is divided into three main chapters:

- French Pilot solutions description
- French inland waterways pilot test results
- Impact assessment of French inland waterways pilot solutions

It describes the seven technologies tested on the French inland waterways during the CRISTAL project: CEDRE, Fluv'IOTe, Smart buoys, SIR, Synchronodal Corridor Management System, Acoustic Emissions and Digital Twin.

The report adopts a systemic approach to present the tested functionalities, the test results, and the potential impact of implementing CRISTAL technologies, according to inland waterway professionals.

2. French Pilot solutions description

This section provides a description of the seven technologies developed in the CRISTAL project and tested on the French Pilot: CEDRE, Fluv'IOTe, Smart Buoys, SIR (subsurface inspection radar), Synchronodal Corridor Management System, Acoustic Emissions, and Digital Twin.

It outlines the objectives and the approach that led to the development of these technologies, as well as their functionalities.

The tests carried out on the French Pilot aim to improve maintenance practices and the competitiveness of inland waterway logistics, in order to enhance the resilience of river transport and promote modal shift.

CEDRE

Technology Objectives:

VNF launched in 2013 a digitized voyage declaration system (VELI – Voyage En Ligne), which now covers nearly all commercial vessel journeys, with approximately 60,000 loaded voyage declarations submitted per year. However, this system, which remains declarative, continues to face certain limitations, most notably, insufficient data reliability.

The objectives of CEDRE were then to simplify administrative procedures for transport declarations by navigators, and to optimize unused transport capacity (empty trips).

The indirect objective is to allow charterers to reduce their operating costs: more goods transported for the same amount of fuel.

CEDRE Approach before Developing the Solution

a) Market Study to Assess Needs

VNF (Voies navigables de France) conducted an extensive consultation with stakeholders of inland waterway freight to identify their needs and to define the specifications for the CEDRE solution. Shippers, freight forwarders, and carriers were consulted, including Ceremis, Senalia, Carré, Soufflet, SCAT, Lalement, STF, and Cemex.

Carriers shared various challenges that may affect the attractiveness of inland waterway freight: aging navigation infrastructure, lock transit times, limited comfort of 38-meter vessels, and conversely, favourable factors such as the existence of significant cargo volumes and the ease of intermodality with rail and road transport.

Operators like STF expressed strong interest in a solution that would reduce empty return trips and proposed piloting the CEDRE solution in collaboration with their shareholder, CFT, incorporating the automated administrative declaration of transported goods.

The CEDRE digital solution thus presents an opportunity to:

- Monitor the full operational activity of units and chartered vessels;
- Eliminate the obligation of manual declarations by sourcing data directly from operators;
- Provide dashboards and statistical reports, while ensuring data protection through role-based access for different stakeholders (shippers, carriers, ports, and VNF).

Automated freight data reporting would also allow stakeholders such as Haropa, responsible for calculating rebates for leaseholders based on traffic volumes, to improve the reliability of their data.

A questionnaire was developed to collect information from clients regarding vessel characteristics (size, handling equipment, CO₂ emissions), quay data (length, storage area, handling equipment, operators, handling rates), and specifics of the waterway transport (duration, freight rates, loading/unloading dates and times, cargo type).

An inventory was taken of existing tools available to clients and logistics stakeholders, such as the SIF Seine, a navigation tool developed by VNF and Haropa (including lock availability, water levels, clearance heights, and navigational notices).

A Business Model Canvas for the CEDRE solution was developed and included in deliverable D8.1.

b) Inventory of Available Market Technologies

VNF conducted a market study of existing technologies, focusing on systems integrating geolocation, databases, transport management systems (TMS), information on transit points, and, in some cases, freight exchanges. VNF engaged with providers of various solutions, including SYGO BV, Dis-Transics, Gedmouv, GPI, ITEM ICARE, Microlise, Novacom CLS, OMP, Transfollow, and Trucknet. SYGO BV, for example, provides cargo traceability from a control station. Its electronic gauging device ensures proper loading and continuously monitors the vessel's fill level and corresponding draft in real-time.

A more targeted market study was conducted to evaluate software vendors capable of developing CEDRE's system architecture, in coordination with VNF's IT department. The following solutions were examined: CLS-Novacom, Ant'IOTE, Logiflu, Abacom, Technema, I-barge, KeeX-MGI, Soget, and around ten other systems primarily used in road transport.

Two solutions were further analyzed in depth: Technema and Keeex/MGI. Their functionalities were assessed against CEDRE's functional requirements. The Keeex/MGI solution emerged as the option for the project that was the most aligned with the functional requirements, and most mature. A diagram showing the analysis of the functionalities and features of the Keeex/MGI solution against the requirements is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Benchmark: analysis of solution KeeX/MGI

c) Development of an Attractive Solution for VNF and Its Users

Several approaches were considered:

- Using a solution such as CLS Novacom to geolocate vessels (tracking routes from origin through lock passages to destination), and, if possible, identifying vessel speed and load level. While this solution does not collect data directly from shippers, it improves the reliability of the available information;
- Developing APIs (Application Programming Interface) that interface with the TMS of transport operators equipped with digital TMSs (15 transport companies identified);
- Upgrading the VELI system to support new functionalities;
- Generating transport documents via ELISE (Electronic Document Management System) already used by VNF for administrative purposes;
- Inferring information on empty vessels by analyzing the end dates of “declared” journeys.

The preferred solution was to develop an API between the VNF Voyages application (VELI) and the transport management systems (TMS) used by inland freight operators.

In this model, the inland waterway carrier's TMS transmits key transport data to Voyages, VNF's central system for managing freight tolls and statistical reporting. Transport documents are thus digitized, secured, and can be modified by authorized stakeholders (carrier, shipper, freight forwarder, and potentially port operators). This removes the obligation to manually declare data in VELI.

Other potential beneficiaries of this shared data include Haropa, CNR (Compagnie Nationale du Rhône), GPMM (Port of Marseille Fos), and Belgian waterways authorities, among others. The system also facilitates the dissemination of information on vessels seeking freight.

VNF also worked on identifying all stages of the voyage process and breaking it down into a “journey workflow” that could enable the data for the process to be digitized.

Figure 2 Summary of an inland waterway tri

In the long term, the ERINOT format should be prioritized as the format to record data related to voyages: ERINOT is the European standard (XML format) for electronic notifications of inland waterways freight transport (including both dangerous and non-dangerous goods) and empty voyages. The ERINOT message enables the transmission of voyage and cargo information for vessels navigating inland waterways.

VNF's IT department has thus developed a set of specifications outlining the anticipated features of the CEDRE solution:

1. Enable data submission by companies in three possible categories:
 - Inland waterways carriers (individual operators, cooperatives, or industrial-scale transport companies),
 - Contracting parties (shippers, whether industrial/commercial enterprises or transport/logistics groups),
 - Freight forwarders (acting as intermediaries between carriers and shippers).
2. Allow these stakeholders to receive and exchange transport documents, such as:
 - Waybills,
 - Inland waterway bills of lading,
 - And potentially other documents to be considered after prototype evaluation (e.g., CDNI compliance certificates: Convention on the Contract for the Carriage of Goods by Inland Waterways).
3. Provide authorized organizations with two types of information:
 - Real-time geolocation of inland waterways vessels, whether docked, moored, or in transit,
 - Estimated time of arrival (ETA) at destination quays, as well as identification and location of vessels with available hold space, including commercial contact details for transport quote requests.
4. Enable VNF to collect the following information for each journey registered on the platform by the stakeholders mentioned above:
 - Loading and unloading quays,
 - Inland waterway route taken,
 - Loading and estimated unloading dates,
 - Type of cargo,
 - Quantity of goods transported.

d) Strategic Importance of Reforming the Freight Toll System

The application also addresses the critical need to secure revenue from freight tolls, which requires reliable data collection from shippers.

In the current "Voyages" process, inland freight carriers are required to declare their routes (origin–destination), loads, and the vessel used before commencing a trip on inland waterways network.

These declarations, including for empty voyages, allow VNF to:

- Invoice freight tolls (based on ton-kilometers) and other applicable charges (e.g., tolls from the International Moselle Company),
- Produce statistical data on network usage for VNF governance, the Ministry for the Ecological Transition, Eurostat, and partners such as Ports de Paris (for port fees and domain fee rebates).

VNF staff currently review and validate voyage declarations to issue toll invoices to carriers (based on a statement of dues). Verification is conducted by cross-checking declaration data (from VELI and VOYAGE systems) with lockkeeper logs (Cahier de l'Éclusier). This process represents a significant administrative cost.

VNF has initiated a redesign of its toll system, which is currently based primarily on the weight (in tonnes) of transported goods, in order to adapt it to evolving freight patterns (urban logistics, containerized cargo, heavy parcels). The goal is to enhance the competitiveness of inland waterways transport while optimizing revenue collection, and to explore the possibility of differentiating toll rates based on cargo type.

However, data collected from barge operators is not always reliable, and only cargo weight is currently captured via the VELI system.

Since journey data is submitted in advance and on a self-declared basis, operators may underreport their load to reduce or avoid tolls and other fees. The CEDRE solution can help improve data accuracy by capturing it at the source, and by differentiating cargo types, thereby enabling more refined and fair toll calculations.

Four main differentiations compared to the state of the art:

- A single trip declaration (empty or loaded) instead of two or three, especially for international journeys.
- Navigators may no longer need to make any declarations, if VNF collects the necessary data via IT gateways between shippers' Transport Management Systems (TMS) and the Voyage API (, a data collection tool for freight statistics and navigation fee billing).
- For a round trip, if the return leg is loaded instead of empty, revenue increases by 75%, and transported tonnage doubles, while fuel consumption and CO₂ emissions rise by only 17%.
- Between 2020 and 2025, 20% of commercial barge trips on VNF's network are empty (approximately 20,000 out of 100,000 total trips) (source: VNF).

Table 2 Table of functionalities for CEDRE

Functionality	Functionality Description	Tested in France	Tested in Italy	Tested in Poland	Data source	Produced data	Data receiver / consumer
Transport Reporting API	API enabling the reception of transport data in the Voyage system, sent from the TMS of an inland waterway carrier (freight forwarder).	Yes (CFT)			TMS of Sogestran	Wharves and departure/arrival dates, type and quantity of goods transported, currency and ENI of the vessel, name of the goods recipient	Transport reporting API (a tool for collecting transport data and billing navigation fees)

Figure 3 Software Architecture : CEDRE

Figure 4 Software functionalities

Features

This is the set of functionalities to be found within the application or solution chosen.

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Fluv'IOTe

Objectives of the technology

The aim of this technology is to geolocate barges on the network and monitor quay occupancy rates.

It enables the identification of available docks through the use of a camera and artificial intelligence, which interpret the aggregated images to determine the presence or absence of barges along the dock.

Fluv'IOTe Approach before Developing the Solution

The Fluv'IOTe project was developed at the request of users such as Cemex and Sogestran, who want to be able to geolocate barges and detect mooring failures or drifting barges.

Several initiatives (experiments and projects) are currently underway at VNF to harness the technological potential of IoT to address the various needs of the inland waterways sector and improve user services. VNF has assessed IoT usage within the Seine Basin Territorial Directorate, covering two main aspects:

- An inventory of existing connected devices on infrastructure assets (dams, locks, water pumps, site lighting, waste collection systems, technical facilities, etc.)

- Identification of additional needs for these infrastructures (requirements not yet addressed by existing IoT solutions)

The identified IoT use cases fall into the following categories:

- Hydraulic management, using data such as water levels, clearance heights, and flow sensors. These data are used and shared via applications like Aghyre and SIF
- Maintenance, with monitoring of dams by local lock operators, which VNF’s modernization project plans to centralize
- Operations, involving remote control and centralized supervision
- User services, and Fluv’IOTe project falls into this category

Five main differentiations compared to the state of the art:

- Geolocation of barges not equipped with AIS-type devices (The AIS, Automatic Identification System, is an automated message exchange system between ships via VHF radio, allowing vessels and traffic surveillance system to know the identity, position, and course of ships within the navigation area)
- Use of cameras to analyse barge mooring areas
- Image processing using a custom-developed AI tailored to the needs of the experiment
- Use of AIS data to reinforce the results obtained through image recognition
- Initial use of AIS track analysis for push boats to infer their activity near barge mooring areas

Table 3 Table of functionality for Fluv’IOTe

Functionality	Functionality Description	Tested in France	Tested in Italy	Tested in Poland	Data source	Produced data	Data receiver / consumer
Barge mooring areas status	A camera captures images which are aggregated and interpret by an AI to identify the mooring area occupancy	Yes			Camera	Image and status of occupancy	Inland waterways carriers

French Smart Buoys

Objectives of the technology

The function of the buoys is to mark the navigable river channel that it is safe for vessels to navigate within. They enable vessels to distinguish the navigable river channel from areas unsuitable for navigations, such as areas near the banks, where the depth of water is generally too shallow, or areas containing obstacles like rocky bottoms.

French Smart Buoys Approach before Developing the Solution

During flood periods, the buoys frequently drift out of the channel, which create safety risks. Local teams need to do regular check-in all along channels in order to replace the buoys and avoid barges accidents.

The selected tool allows for regular verification of buoy presence within their designated swing area and, if the buoys are detected outside of their designated area, or not detected at all, it automatically triggers an alert. This alert enables the operations team to inform users via Avisbat (Notice to Skippers) about the incident and allows the maintenance team to schedule corrective actions. The system also monitors the status of light signals installed on the buoys to improve nighttime visibility. These lights are automatically switched off when the buoy is no longer in position.

Three main differentiations compared to the state of the art:

- Remote transmission of buoy positions
- Automatic alert when a buoy moves outside its designated swing area
- Visual light signals for users to ensure safe navigation at night

Table 4 Table of functionalities for French smart buoys

Functionality	Functionality Description	Tested in France	Tested in Italy	Tested in Poland	Data source	Produced data	Data receiver / consumer
Positioning	GNSS positioning	Yes			GNSS map integrated into the beacon	WGS84 position in decimal degrees format	Remote control platform and waterways management system
Automatic zone exit alert	The position of each buoy is compared to its defined swing radius. An alert is sent if the	Yes			Remote control platform	Sending an email and SMS to the relevant services	Inland Waterways manager (operations and maintenance)

	buoy exits this radius.					and personnel.	
Lighting signals	Emission of a flash in the colour of the buoy.	Yes				None	Waterway user in direct view of the light

SIR Technology (UNEW/EUROMOBILITA)

Objectives of the technology

The radar based non-destructive sub-surface inspection system (SIR) was designed for examination and inspection of inland waterways infrastructure assets. The technology aims to assess the integrity of the inspected assets and provide information on their condition, which would enable preventive and/or predictive maintenance. Therefore, the goal of using SIR technology is that, by enabling improved maintenance practices, to efficiently contribute toward improving the reliability and resilience of assets. The technology's description will be more detailed in D8.3.

Five main differentiations compared to the state of the art:

Currently, visual inspections of lock chambers are carried out within scheduled maintenance activities. Typically, just a limited number of potential issues can be detected through visual inspection, and mostly surface ones. Otherwise, defects might only be detected when issues become apparent, such as obvious failures of infrastructure, or issues with the stability of surrounding land, which would have to be responded to with expensive and disruptive reactive maintenance and repair. The main advantages of using the SIR technology are listed below:

- SIR uses State-of-the-Art radar techniques designed for in-depth scanning (Ground Penetrating Radar - GPR), which is typically used for earthworks, masonry and concrete structure inspection depending on the specific application. GPR surveys typically detect, localise and profile features (i.e., structural anomalies) concealed within such subsurface media. Returned data can be analysed to determine both quantitative (e.g., depth, footprint, etc.) and qualitative (e.g., shape, complexity, composition, etc.) feature properties. Features can be identified within unknown subsurface topography but are more commonly analysed in topographies where some prior insight into subsurface condition exists (e.g., a prior survey using GPR or other technology, construction records, etc).
- SIR technology was designed to allow semi-automated subsurface inspection of vertical and sloping walls or structures (such as lock walls and dams), as opposed to conventional GPR, which is manually operated and most frequently applied to horizontal surfaces (i.e., the ground).
- SIR facilitates direct targeted inspection of potential problem areas that have been previously identified through visual inspection/observation.

- The technology allows accurate identification of voids and various abnormalities within the scanned structures or the ground around them.
- Repeated recordings of SIR scan results of the same region of a structure over long time scales allows for initially benchmarking the inspected infrastructure and then monitoring potential issues to determine the progression of failures, which would inform for predictive and preventative maintenance.

Table 5 Table of functionalities for SIR

Functionality	Functionality Description	Tested in France	Tested in Italy	Tested in Poland	Produced data	Data receiver / consumer
F1 Identification of features of interest (Fol)	Detects and highlights the presence of a subsurface structural anomaly within the surveyed subsurface topography.	Yes	No	No	2D Slices/ Heatmaps + 3D Isosurfaces	Infra manager
F2 Scaling of Fols	Returned output data formats capable of relaying the relative shapes, volumes and separations of identified Fols.	Yes	No	No	2D Slices/ Heatmaps + 3D Isosurfaces + Volume estimates	Infra manager
F3 Localisation of Fols	Relays the extent of the footprint for a particular Fol and its defining position with respect to the surveyed region/full structure.	Yes	No	No	2D Slices/ Heatmaps + 3D Isosurfaces	Infra manager
F4 Visualisation of Fols	Generates multimedia (e.g., image, video, 3D files) capable of visually conveying the 2D/3D spatial profiles of structural anomalies within the subsurface topography.	Yes	No	No	2D Slices/ Heatmaps + 3D Isosurfaces + Orbital Videos + 2D Projections of 3D Isosurfaces	Infra manager
F5 Targeted inspection of specific areas	Deployable across the full extent of a structure and on localised regions of a particular structure.	Yes	No	No	As Above	Infra manager

F6 Recording of data	Captures individual data files storing the amplitude of the radar signal at fixed time intervals, encoding the response profiles of radar signal reflected from the subsurface and any artifacts associated with the condition of the topography.	Yes	No	No	Specific radar equipment files (e.g., SEG-Y Files)	Infra manager
F7 Adaptability for use on different structural aspects/use cases	Capable of operating in multiple different configurations (e.g., vertical, horizontal, in conjunction with operating setup) to be able to inspect lock walls and surrounding lock-side areas, and/or other structures (e.g., dams, ground).	Yes	No	No	As above	Infra manager

Synchromodal Corridor Management System (CERTH)

Objectives of the technology

The Synchromodal Corridor Management System (SCMS) aims to increase inland navigation reliability and modal share by providing better visibility of river navigability status to stakeholders and also by improving the integration of inland navigation systems to multimodal transport corridors.

Synchromodality is a logistics approach that enables the seamless and flexible integration of various transport modes; such as road, rail, inland waterways, and maritime; within a single supply chain. The most suitable mode, or combination of modes, is selected in real time based on factors like cost efficiency, environmental impact, congestion, and delivery requirements. The SCMS software architecture is detailed in Figure 5 below and the technology's description is more detailed in D3.1.

Two main differentiations compared to the state of the art:

- The system estimates the navigability status of the river for assessing planned routes not only considering the current situation (existing published alerts) but also considering forecasted

issues through its connection to the Digital Twins of the project (i.e. forecasting water depths and infrastructure(lock) failure)

- The system is a single place (one-stop-shop) for gaining visibility to the river status regarding navigability and the alternatives through the other land modes of transport (road/rail).

Table 6 Table of functionalities for Corridor Management System

Functionality	Functionality Description	Tested in France	Tested in Italy	Tested in Poland	Data source	Produced data	Data receiver / consumer
Early info and alert	Collection of existing and forecasted alerts (through DTs) and distribution to relevant stakeholders	yes	yes	yes	infrastructure managers, DT, civil protection services, weather services and any other service that publishes alert for rivers	List of alerts	Operational stakeholders (e.g. barge operators, 3PL companies)
Route planning assessment	Assessment of the feasibility of a route in a river based on the time plan, vessel characteristic and the existing and forecasted alerts	yes	yes	yes	(User defined: Vessel characteristic, day/time of journey, origin-destination) Collection of alerts from early info and alert functionality, google maps for calculating the road leg of the transport	Optimal route, List of alerts affecting planned river routes	Operational stakeholders (e.g. barge operators, 3PL companies)
Synchromodal replanning		yes	yes	yes	(User defined, day/time of journey, origin-destination) Google maps for road alternatives,	Alternative routes (description & display on map)	Inland Waterways operational stakeholders (e.g. barge operators, 3PL companies)

					OpenRailwayMap for rail network		
Observatory		yes	yes	yes	Collection of alerts from early info and alert functionality, infrastructure data (type, characteristics, position) from infrastructure managers	Analytics on infrastructure reliability (i.e. locks) and river navigability	Inland Waterways operational stakeholders (e.g. barge operators, 3PL companies), Infrastructure managers, public administration

Figure 5 SCMS : details of the software architecture

Acoustic Emissions (CERTH)

Objectives of the technology

To predict upcoming failures of the metallic lock gates on waterways, enabling predictive maintenance practices to be implemented, based on the warnings of failures. The software developed for this technology is delayed Figure 6 below.

Five main differentiations compared to the state of the art:

- Extremely easy installation and deployment.
- Non experts can deploy the apparatus and the results are automatically transferred to the Digital Twin and for the interpretation of the results no expertise is required.

- Safety during operation and installation.
- It can be deployed periodically and does not require the operation of the lock to be suspended for the installation to take place.
- Extremely sensitivity in capturing elastic waves produced by early failing mechanisms.

Table 7 Table of functionalities for Acoustic Emissions

Functionality	Description of functionality	Tested in France	Tested in Italy	Tested in Poland
The system shall detect acoustic emissions related to structural anomalies.	Sensitivity to detect mechanical elastic waves in the metal.	yes	yes	no
The system shall localize the source of emissions on the gate surface.	Within a radius of 0.5m for prediction of microcracks and other causes of failure on gates parts and 2.5 m direct impact from a foreign object	yes	yes	no
The system shall log and timestamp acoustic events for post-analysis.	Data storage compatible with cloud services.	yes	yes	no
Scalability on the number of installed sensors across the water-lock gate	Adding multi-channel AE loggers or many from the used 4 channel logger.	yes	yes	no
Detecting metal microcracks before major metal crack failures and detecting upcoming out of the normal operation failures.	Detecting metal microcracks before major metal crack failures and detecting upcoming out of the normal operation failures (by positioning sensors close to gate parts under inspection various kind of failures can be detected, e.x. near	yes	yes	no

	<p>pistons or at the bottom of the gate buildup of canal precipitations)</p>			
<p>The inspection system shall provide the end-user with the necessary assessment data for making appropriate decision in response to upcoming failures in the gate</p>	<p>The system provides streaming with confidence levels (assessments) on detected microcracks and/or out of normal operation patterns. The raising frequency or raising amplitude in comparison to past AE recordings is an assessment indication which indicates a possible nearby predictive maintenance cycle.</p>	<p>yes</p>	<p>yes</p>	<p>no</p>

Figure 6 Acoustic emissions: software architecture

Digital Twin (Fraunhofer)

Objectives of the technology

Allow carriers to anticipate navigability and infrastructure malfunctions to optimize their travel time. For waterway managers, digital twins provide a solution for analysis and predictive maintenance.

A digital twin is a system consisting of two parts. The first part is the physical component. The second part is a new virtual component, which holds all the data of the physical system. As a result, a replica of the system is created, spanning from the virtual realm to the physical world.

The digital twin can, for example, provide a better overview of assets and facilitate daily maintenance. It allows access to precise data that is usually inaccessible and makes it available through a simple and accessible interface. The digital twin can also predict the future status of the asset based on gathered historical information and ease predictive maintenance and navigation forecast.

Three kinds of Digital twin are tested in the CRISTAL project:

- Digital twin of Locks
 - Technical information on the locks
 - Results from AE sensors
 - Results from SIR inspections on the structure
 - Maintenance data specifications, especially regarding lock closures
- Digital twin of smart buoys
 - Data visualization: water level, ice thickness, wind speed, geolocation
 - Ability to set alarms with threshold values corresponding to different types of boats
 - Visualization of buoys on a map
- Digital Twin of water level
 - Predictions of water levels based on precipitation, etc.
 - Verification of navigability forecasts for different types of boats
 - Expected location and extent of sandbanks

The software architecture of this technology is described in Figure 7 below, and the technology's description is more detailed in D5.1.

Key Innovations Compared to Existing Digital Twin Solutions:

While digital twins are increasingly used across various sectors, their application in inland waterways remains limited in scope and integration. The CRISTAL Digital Twin stands out by combining real-time data from multiple infrastructure elements, locks, smart buoys, and water levels; into a single, interoperable platform that supports both operational and strategic decision-making.

The solution advances beyond existing digital twin implementations in several key ways:

- Integrated multi-asset monitoring: Unlike conventional approaches that focus on isolated components, CRISTAL integrates data across the entire waterway system. This includes:
 - Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR) technology for visualizing the internal condition of lock walls.
 - Acoustic Emission (AE) systems that assess and forecast the structural health of lock doors.
 - Smart buoys that collect environmental and navigational data, such as water level, ice thickness, and wind speed.
- Predictive capabilities and early warning systems: The CRISTAL Digital Twin enables predictive maintenance and early failure detection through:

- Alerts on lock door failure risk when it exceeds pre-set thresholds.
- Forecasting of water level and navigability conditions based on historical and real-time data.
- Enhanced user interaction and data visualization: CRISTAL’s interface allows users to visualize, input, and manage:
 - Lock chamber dimensions and general status.
 - Buoy positions and threshold alarms for various vessel types.
 - Lock-related documents and metadata in a centralised system.
- Support for corridor-level decision making: The system is designed not just for asset-level management, but also to feed into the broader Corridor Management System (CMS), enabling authorities to anticipate disruptions and optimize navigational planning across the entire inland waterway network.

In summary, the Digital Twin approach offers a holistic, data-driven, and predictive infrastructure management tool that significantly improves upon current digital twin applications in the inland waterway domain.

Table 8 Table of functionalities for Digital twin

Functionality	Functionality Description	Data source	Produced data	Data receiver / consumer
Maintenance	Analysis of data from acoustic sensors, the detection of anomalies, and the anticipation of malfunctions during operation, enabling planning and scheduling of maintenance. It recognizes typical patterns in data, allowing it to detect and predict issues using machine learning.	Infrastructure managers, AE, SIR	Alerts and predictions	Operational stakeholders (e.g. VNF, barge operators, 3PL companies); alerts for users, predictions for infrastructure managers
Navigability	Produce alerts and predictive analyses of water levels and flow rates by processing historical and sensor data.	Infrastructure managers, buoys, civil protection services, weather services and any other service that publishes alert for rivers	Alerts and predictions	Operational stakeholders (e.g. VNF, barge operators, 3PL companies); alerts for users, predictions for infrastructure managers

Buoy positioning	Identification of the unexpected movements of buoys marking the channels in order to facilitate maintenance and navigability	Smart buoys	Map shows where the buoy should be and where it is; transfer of a simple alert to the SCMS when the threshold of 3m has been exceeded	VNF
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Only functionalities 1 and 3 were tested as part of the French pilot (DT Lock: maintenance; DT buoys: buoys positioning).

Figure 7 Digital twins: software architecture

Digital Twin Buoy

Digital Twin Water Level

3. French inland waterways pilot test results

The seven technologies from the CRISTAL project presented in the previous section were tested as part of the French pilot, in order to assess the conditions and practicalities of their implementation in the field. The aim is also to identify the most effective functionalities in relation to the goals of strengthening the resilience of inland freight transport, promoting modal shift, and improving maintenance practices.

Some of these tests (such as SIR) are still ongoing, and their final results will be presented in the deliverables dedicated to these technologies.

Each of the tested technologies is described in a dedicated subsection. Each subsection presents the operating characteristics of the tests, the data collected, their processing, and the conclusions drawn from the test results.

CEDRE

a) Operating characteristics

Environment requirements

Transport of a commercial vessel, either solo or in a pushed convoy, preferably loaded, on a waterway managed by VNF; equipped with non-digitalized transport documents on board.

Test method and steps

Three categories of data are required for CEDRE:

- Geographic (from where to where, and when)
- The vessel owner
- The nature and quantity of the cargo

Some barges are not equipped with geolocation systems, as they are only installed on pushers.

A test was carried out with equipment provider CLS Novacom, a subsidiary of CNES, which was among the technologies identified on the market. This responded to a request from Cemex to locate its drifting barges. Cemex was satisfied and is now equipping its 100 barges with energy-autonomous sensors from this brand.

VNF chose not to use this technology itself but to collect data from the TMS by establishing an IT gateway with CFT and Cemex.

An initial IT gateway has been established with CFT Sogestran, which is now connected to the VNF travel database.

This company operates 200 vessels and is seeking a more efficient application than VELI, so that goods declarations are no longer handled by vessels crews but are instead transmitted electronically. This was implemented as part of their CMS update and is working well. Once the data is pooled, it will be converted into the ERINOT format so it can be shared with other ports such as Haropa and with VNF's international counterparts.

This feature is currently being developed, with the data undergoing conversion as part of the CRISTAL project (work in progress).

The connection with CFT has been under testing for a year and is operational, although some data is occasionally received incorrectly.

To redesign its toll system, a dedicated methodology has been established by VNF to support this overhaul, enabling an assessment of the toll's share in the total cost of inland waterway transport, compared to road freight pricing.

Key origin-destination-product combinations have been identified within each regional directorate (Hauts-de-France, Seine Basin, North-East, and Rhône-Saône). For each combination, the total cost of waterway transport is estimated (including pre- and post-haulage and handling), as well as the equivalent road transport cost. The toll price is then modelled based on several parameters.

b) **Data collected**

Geographical transport data: loading and unloading dates and quays, in France (at least one of the two) or not. Type (NST: Standard Goods Nomenclature for Transport Statistics) and quantity of cargo transported (with or without commercial value – e.g., various waste); in a unit of measurement to be defined according to the type of cargo (tons, cubic meters, units, TEU or FEU, pallets, etc.) Currency (name) and the vessel's unique European registration number (ENI) Company name of the consignor (shipper)

c) **Data processing**

Reception of data into the VNF Voyage database (VELI) for:

- Production of transport statistics by VNF:
 - For the Ministry of Transport, the European Commission, or the Central Commission for the Navigation of the Rhine (CCNR).
 - Statistics for "private" clients (statistics on quay usage, vessels, types of vessels, etc.)
 - Statistics on the use of specific waterways for VNF, to support investment policies and the evolution of operational staff.
- Billing of various fees:
 - VNF navigation fees.
 - Potentially, contributions to various organizations whose collection is entrusted to VNF.

d) Functionality performance summary and details

Table 9 Functionality performance for CEDRE

Test ID	Functionality	Test description	Expected outcome	Actual Outcome	Status	Remarks / cause if failure
T0001	Voyage API (TMS – VNF integration)	Automatic transmission of transport data (e.g., quay, date, cargo, ENI) from CFT's TMS to VNF's "Voyage" database via an API using the ERINOT format.	Reduce manual declarations by crews, improve data quality, simplify administrative processes.	Successfully tested at CFT. Data transmitted and received correctly. Some format/integration issues were identified and corrected during testing.	Successful (minor corrections required)	Technical adjustments were needed for data integration and some format compliance (e.g., missing fields, XML structure).
T0002	Reduction of empty voyages	Evaluation of CEDRE's potential impact on reducing empty trips through improved logistical coordination	Optimize transport capacity, reduce empty runs, increase visibility on available trips.	Specific module to identify vessels waiting for cargo was not developed due to reluctance from certain charterers to share availability data.	Partially completed	Lack of stakeholder willingness to share data on vessel availability limited full implementation.
T0003	Data use for invoicing and statistics	Test of automated collection of transport data into VNF's "Voyage" database for invoicing and statistical reporting.	Enable automatic production of statistics (for Ministry of Transport, CCNR) and invoicing of navigation fees.	Data was successfully integrated into the "Voyage" system and is usable for statistical reporting and invoicing purposes.	Successful	N/A

T0004	Redesign of the toll system	Development of a new methodology to propose a toll that fit the market as it currently is	A new toll that integrates all type of boats and all types of transported goods	The methodology has been developed but it is not implemented yet	Partially completed	N/A
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e) Conclusions based on results analysis

The test version is deployed with two operators (CFT and Cemex) to identify any issues (e.g., poor integration of certain data) and resolve them. The process is finalised with CFT and evidences the proper functioning of the technology. The process is ongoing for Cemex.

VNF is planning the proposal of this test version to a dozen chartering companies, with some of the IT development costs covered as part of a multimodal shift & greening program financed by the Energy Saving Certificates (CEE).

An analysis of the data from TMS must be carried out by VNF in order to build standardized databases that can be translated into the ERINOT format and exchanged with ports such as Haropa and European inland waterway operators.

f) Impact assessment on KPI's, relevant or irrelevant functionalities to improve reliability, maintenance and modal shift

Impact on modal shift (indirect effect):

The advantage of this technology is its ability to optimize VNF staff's (data collection) or the carrier's staff's (avoiding declarations by navigators) time for data collection and transmission. It therefore reduce the administrative costs implied by using IWT.

A more comprehensive collection of information on the nature and volume of transported goods enables inland waterway operators to produce useful statistics for optimizing routes and transport infrastructures, as well as for calculating fees.

However, data-sharing module for vessels operating empty has not yet been designed, due to the reluctance of certain market players (notably freight forwarders).

Fluv'IOTe

a) Operating characteristics

Environment requirements

The Fluv'IOTe system requires the use of a camera on a high point with an unobstructed view of the supervised infrastructure. The presence of buildings and vegetation limits deployment possibilities.

Test method and steps

Three kinds of tests were carried out: with geolocation modules on barges, with a camera on wharfs, and a third combining both.

The first series of tests were experimentations requiring the installation of modules on barges. The company CFT provided its barges so that the experimentation could focus on the real movements of real objects.

The experimentation was carried out in June 2022 with the ToughTracker distributed by BigVista. It is a standalone GPS/Cellular unit whose data is sent to the RiverIN client platform. This platform features a cartographic display allowing the position of the modules to be viewed. An API (Application Programming Interface) was developed to deliver the position data to the SIF of VNF.

The equipped barges transmit location information every hour to the SIF (River Information System of VNF). The information transmitted includes barge name, longitude, latitude, timestamp.

The beacons were deployed for 1 month on barges (see location in Figure 8 below). This duration is explained by the fact that no additional power supply was installed. Indeed, market-based geolocation devices are designed to be connected to a power source or to emit on frequencies that are not compatible with the needs of shipowners and infrastructure managers.

Figure 8 Location of CFT barge

The second series of tests were conducted with cameras and took place over a period of 2 months during 2023. The site is located in Paris 16th arrondissement: Quai Louis Blériot (see more details on the location figure 9 below), where the camera has been installed. The Louis Blériot site extends linearly and covers a distance of 600 meters. Berthing on this quay is straightforward. The camera is positioned on the opposite quay to cover the entire parking area.

Figure 9 Location of the test in Paris

This allowed for the collection of numerous images. It should be noted that the AI training started on a car parking lot to lay the groundwork for the detection solution while waiting for the actual deployment in Paris. Also, a third approach has been tested, combining Camera + AIS + AI.

Images collected during a previous test using high-resolution cameras were cross-referenced with AIS (Automatic Identification System) data gathered over the same period to explore correlations between visual quay occupancy and vessel movements. This work was conducted in the framework of the Fluv'IOTE project, led by VNF and CSTN, with support from CFT, and included contributions from an internship carried out by Negin Arianfar between March and August 2023. The field testing phase took place from July to September 2023 at the Louis Blériot quay in Paris, where the experimental setup included fixed cameras capturing real-time images and the collection of AIS data from pusher vessels.

The objective was to detect events of barge deposit and retrieval and to understand pusher behaviour in relation to quay usage. Three years of AIS data were processed using trajectory segmentation and geofencing techniques to isolate relevant movement patterns. These were then manually labelled to build a training dataset for supervised machine learning models, including Random Forest and Support Vector Machines. To accelerate development, the AI model was initially trained on imagery from a parking lot before being applied to actual quay environments.

This approach enabled the combination of trajectory data analysis and advanced modelling techniques to forecast barge deposits, retrievals, and pass-throughs without docking. Results were promising: the system successfully identified pusher positions and associated activities, achieving around 85% accuracy on labelled validation samples. However, the overall predictive performance remains constrained by the quality of AIS data, particularly due to inconsistencies in convoy configuration updates by operators. The study demonstrated the feasibility of using combined visual and AIS data to monitor and anticipate quay occupancy, while also highlighting the need for more extensive training data and improved data quality to support operational scaling and decision-making.

b) Data processing

Assembly: Capture several images with overlap to stitch them into a panoramic image, followed by automatic calculation based on the area to be monitored. Automatic creation of a cropped panoramic image according to the defined parameters, including the right, left, top, and bottom boundaries.

Figure 10 Examples of images captured on Quay Louis Blériot

Detection: Identification and search for barges

Occupancy calculation: Determining the free and occupied areas. Estimation of the width of each area (including distortion correction). The analysis results show that three barges were detected with a very high certainty. The camera system was validated on a single quay.

Figure 11 Occupancy calculation

	available	device_id	dock_id	dock_width	filename	occupied	timestamp
0	[[[10.5, 15], [35, 60.79999923706055], [105, 16...	CAM001232	QUAI23423	627.5	2022-04-03_16-35-15.jpg	[[[0, 10.5], [15, 35], [60.79999923706055, 105]...	2022-04-03 16:35:15+00:00
1	[[[10.5, 15], [35, 60.79999923706055], [105, 16...	CAM001232	QUAI23423	627.5	2023-02-27_09-35-15.jpg	[[[0, 10.5], [15, 35], [60.79999923706055, 105]...	2023-02-27 09:35:15+00:00
2	[[[0, 395.739990234375], [407.760009765625, 668]]	CAM001232	QUAI23423	668.0	2023-12-08_12-40-01.jpg	[[[395.739990234375, 407.760009765625]]	2023-12-08 12:40:01+00:00
3	[[[0, 649.2999877929688], [667.9299926757812, 6...	CAM001232	QUAI23423	668.0	2023-12-08_13-20-01.jpg	[[[649.2999877929688, 667.9299926757812]]	2023-12-08 13:20:01+00:00
4	[[[0, 0], [4.099999904632568, 668]]	CAM001232	QUAI23423	668.0	2023-12-08_13-40-01.jpg	[[[0, 4.099999904632568]]	2023-12-08 13:40:01+00:00
...
2585	[[[0, 30.649999618530273], [73.81999969482422, ...	CAM001232	QUAI23423	668.0	2024-03-13_12-00-01.jpg	[[[30.649999618530273, 73.81999969482422], [572...	2024-03-13 12:00:01+00:00
2586	[[[0, 30.700000762939453], [73.9000015258789, 5...	CAM001232	QUAI23423	668.0	2024-03-13_12-10-02.jpg	[[[30.700000762939453, 73.9000015258789], [571...	2024-03-13 12:10:02+00:00
2587	[[[0, 30.639999389648438], [73.63999938964844, ...	CAM001232	QUAI23423	668.0	2024-03-13_12-20-01.jpg	[[[30.639999389648438, 73.63999938964844], [581...	2024-03-13 12:20:01+00:00
2588	[[[0, 557.0900268554688], [643.25, 668]]	CAM001232	QUAI23423	668.0	2024-03-13_12-30-01.jpg	[[[557.0900268554688, 643.25]]	2024-03-13 12:30:01+00:00
2589	[[[0, 35.439998626708984], [86.41000366210938, ...	CAM001232	QUAI23423	668.0	2024-03-13_12-40-01.jpg	[[[35.439998626708984, 86.41000366210938]]	2024-03-13 12:40:01+00:00

2590 rows * 7 columns

The final interpretation of the data by VNF's Information System has not been carried out on a longer duration yet. The Fluv'IOTe data processing API will not be developed in the frame of CRISTAL Project, and the "Data Lake", IT solution capable of connecting cameras and sensors and providing network-wide information on quay availability, remains at the concept stage.

Figure 12 Components of an IoT Data Lake

c) Conclusions on results analysis

Out of the three technologies tested, the one involving the deployment of GPS beacons on barges is currently preferred by shipowners. This preference stems from their operational familiarity and the relative simplicity of deployment, rather than from superior technical performance. Following the tests carried out as part of the CRISTAL project, CFT and Cemex have begun equipping all barges in their fleets with geolocation systems. One of the devices tested, equivalent to a Celeste Novacom beacon but lacking an accelerometer, revealed some operational limitations. These included latency in data transmission due to update intervals, particularly when the barge moved away from the dock. This highlighted the importance of integrating acceleration measurement, enabling faster response in the event of unintentional unmooring.

Algorithms based solely on AIS location data for detecting barge mooring remain insufficiently reliable. Although promising accuracy levels were observed in controlled conditions (up to 85% on labelled validation samples), the overall predictive performance is constrained by the quality of AIS data. A key limitation is the inconsistent updating of convoy configurations by pusher crews, especially when transitioning between barge-only and barge + pusher setups. This affects the reliability of standalone AIS-based solutions and limits their operational scalability.

The other technologies tested, Camera + AI, Camera + AIS + AI, and AIS + AI, have demonstrated strong potential in controlled trials. These systems are non-intrusive, require no onboard equipment, and allow passive monitoring of quay occupancy. The hybrid approach (Camera + AIS + AI), in particular, reinforced detection accuracy and confidence during pilot testing. However, these solutions still require further data training, broader validation across sites, and improved AIS consistency to become fully operational. When deployment conditions allow, the use of AIS data also enhances the performance of camera-based systems by reinforcing visual interpretations.

Table 10 Fluv'IOTe Technologies – Summary of Tests and Results

Technology	Test Setup	Result	Limitations
GPS Beacon on Barge	Celeste Novacom-type beacon without accelerometer	Position detected reliably; adopted by CFT/Cemex	Latency in movement detection; no accelerometer; reactive, not predictive
AIS + AI	3 years of AIS data + ML model (Random Forest, SVM)	~85% accuracy on labeled data; able to identify deposits/retrievals	Inconsistent data due to convoy updates; needs high-quality input
Camera + AI	High-res quay imagery (initially trained on parking lot imagery)	Good potential for non-intrusive detection	Requires infrastructure; model not yet generalised
Camera + AIS + AI	Fusion of video feed + AIS trajectory analysis	Strongest performance in pilot phase; reinforced confidence in detection	Still in pilot; requires further operational validation

d) Functionality performance summary and details**Table 11 Functionality performance of Fluv'IOTe Technologies**

Test ID	Functionality	Test description	Expected outcome	Actual Outcome	Status	Remarks / cause if failure
T0001	GPS Beacon on Barges	Deployment of standalone GPS beacons (similar to Celeste Novacom model) on barges for 1 month. No external power source.	Continuous geolocation of barges; enable tracking even without AIS	Position tracking was functional; however, latency and absence of accelerometer limited responsiveness	Partially successful	No accelerometer; delayed updates during movement; reactive system only.

T0002	AIS + AI (pusher analysis)	Analysis of AIS traces over 3 years using ML models (Random Forest, SVM) to detect deposit/retrieval/passing through events based on pusher movement.	Identification of barge-related events with good predictive accuracy	~85% accuracy on labelled samples; feasible detection of barge events	Successful (pilot level)	Constrained by inconsistent convoy length updates in AIS data.
T0003	Camera + AI (image-based detection)	2-month camera-based observation at Louis Blériot quay in Paris. Initial AI training done on parking lot imagery, then adapted to barge context.	Reliable visual detection of barge presence	Effective in detecting presence visually; limited to sites with suitable infrastructure (high vantage points, clear view)	Successful (site-limited)	Limited scalability due to camera placement constraints (obstructions, angles).
T0004	Camera + AIS + AI (hybrid system)	Fusion of video imagery and AIS data to reinforce prediction accuracy of quay occupancy and barge activity.	Enhanced detection and confidence levels through data cross-referencing	Strongest detection performance; system benefited from data redundancy (visual + AIS)	Promising (pilot)	Needs further training data and validation in other locations.

e) Impact assessment on KPI's, relevant or irrelevant functionalities to improve reliability, maintenance and modal shift

This technology has an impact on IWW reliability.

- The geolocation of inland shipments is a service that can enhance navigation safety (e.g., detecting shipments and vessels out of place due to, or mooring line breakages) and offer waterway users technologies that are widely used in the road transport sector, for example.
- As well, the dissemination of quay availability information helps ensure the reliability of freight shipping schedules for carriers and optimizes staff time.

French Smart Buoys

a) Operating characteristics

Environment requirements

Deployment in real conditions in an easily accessible area to facilitate inspections and interventions.

Creating smart buoys installing lights on navigation buoys in water, within an environment similar to the conditions of a navigable waterway.

Test method and steps

The buoys equipped with lights were installed in an old small-scale canal, right next to a VNF workshop. They remained in place from April 2023 to December 2024 to test solar panel recharging under various sunlight conditions and durations. The remote-control gateway was installed in an office to allow for configuration of the lights and visualization of the data.

The initial parameters of the Smart buoys were lights turned on during the nighttime, with the gateway querying the buoy's position every six hours. If the reported position deviated from a predefined zone (a 10-meter radius around the intended placement location) an email and SMS alert were automatically sent to the registered contact.

Test reports and documentation

With the initial settings, the energy capacity of the Smart buoy was sufficient, but we noticed an imprecise reporting of the position that triggered false alarms.

To address this issue, the Smart Buoy is queried more frequently (every two hours) and an alarm is only triggered if three consecutive position reports fall outside the defined zone. However, to avoid false "buoy out of position" alarms, the zone centered on the buoy's intended placement had to be defined with a minimum radius of 20 meters.

This 20-meter radius, however, exceeds the acceptable tolerance for the buoy to still be considered as accurately marking the safe navigable channel. In other words, for the Smart Buoy to reliably indicate that it is no longer within the safe marking zone (without generating false alarms) it would need to report its position with greater accuracy.

Additionally, solar panel recharging is no longer sufficient to keep the batteries charged, especially under low-light conditions.

b) Data collected

GNSS positioning data from the smart buoys.

c) **Data processing**

Visualization and export of data via the remote-control platform. Immediate use of data by maintenance operators through the platform and by waterway users via the visualization of lights in CEVNI format.

d) **Functionality performance summary and details****Table 12 Functionality performance for French smart buoys**

Test ID	Functionality	Test description	Expected outcome	Actual Outcome	Status	Remarks / cause if failure
T0001	Positioning	Deployment of the light in operational conditions	Recording of buoy positions via a GNSS system with an uncertainty of less than 10m	The lights transmit their position correctly, but the uncertainty is greater than 15m	Partially successful	The light is equipped with an integrated GNSS module, but it is not accurate enough
T0001	Automatic zone exit alert	Deployment of the light under operational conditions	Sending an email and SMS to the registered contacts when the reported position of the buoy is outside of the limits of the zone, and tracking positions via the remote control gateway	Consistent with the expected outcomes	Successful	
T0001	Navigation light signal	Deployment of the light under operational conditions	Synchronized light signals, night-visible and aligned with the buoyage system	Consistent with the expected outcomes	Successful	
T0001	Battery capacity and solar panel charging	Deployment of the light under	System energy autonomy at all times and in all season	After increasing the buoy's wake-up frequency to address	Not successful	Consistent with the expected outcomes when the

		operational conditions		positioning issues, energy insufficiency appeared, becoming most apparent during periods of low sunlight.		equipment is used under non-intensive conditions
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e) Conclusions on results analysis

The connected light, as purchased (a complete solution), does not meet the technical criteria set for positioning, but the technology holds significant potential. This smart buoy system is already in use in maritime contexts, though it has not yet been adapted to inland waterways. One of the major challenges encountered during the test was that surrounding trees and hillsides obstructed sunlight from reaching the solar panels, preventing the buoys' batteries from recharging. As a result, the energy generated was insufficient to support the full operation of the smart buoy.

While the LED light used for illumination and navigation visibility consumes very little power, the GNSS module, which is essential for accurately geolocating the buoy and confirming it remains in position to mark the channel, has a high rate of energy consumption. The system is designed to trigger an alert only if three consecutive data readings indicate that the buoy has moved, to avoid false positives. However, false alerts were frequent during testing, which further highlighted limitations in energy supply and system precision.

It would be necessary to work with the supplier to design a buoy that is either more energy-autonomous or consumes less energy. In parallel, improving the accuracy and quality of the transmitted geolocation data is essential. This includes increasing the number of satellite constellations observed (American GPS, European Galileo, Russian GLONASS) to improve positional reliability. Buoys should be equipped with a multi-constellation GNSS receiver to obtain more precise and stable data.

The final phase of testing, planned to take place on a navigable section of the Moselle, could not be carried out due to poor functioning of the buoys. Instead, the tests were limited to a non-navigated reach of the Moselle and conducted during daylight hours. Because of the buoys' performance issues, particularly the failure to transmit data, the trials could not be completed. As a consequence, there was no user feedback regarding the lighting system's effectiveness for night navigation. Moving forward, VNF may consider developing its own smart buoy system in partnership with a service provider, based on a different electronic board equipped with a multi-satellite positioning system tailored to meet inland waterway requirements.

- f) **Impact assessment** on KPIs, relevant or irrelevant functionalities to improve reliability, maintenance and modal shift

The targeted impacts of this technology were to improve maintenance efficiency and reliability of IWW.

The displacement alert was supposed to eliminate the need to deploy a verification team after each flood and allows for immediate notification to quickly warn waterway users of the danger, the lighting system ensuring night navigation safety.

As well, this technology was to reduce the risk of accidents for vessels in the event of an unexpected loss of channel marking by the buoys, and to reduce maintenance time.

As the technology is not functioning properly, it does not have impact.

Subsurface Radar Inspection (SIR) Technology (UNEW/EUROMOBILITA)

a) Operating characteristics

Environment requirements

Summary (more details in D6.2):

Water level in the lock is required to be as low as possible prior to testing.

Accessibility: The Modular Operating Platform is moved into position for scanning on a lock wall by a crane capable of lifting 300kg at the distance from the locations the crane can access and operate from, to the scanning locations. There needs to be access for the crane in close proximity to the lock wall.

Temperature Extremes: Subsurface inspection system operates between -20°C to 60°C internal temperature, the limitation is the electronics system. Power supply: Access is required to a mains power supply to the Modular Operating Platform Power Unit (UK/EU mains 220-249V 50Hz AC).

General Requirements

Surface and Structure Preparation:

The subsurface inspection radar is constructed with a Modular Operating Platform (MOP) that is the physical apparatus providing the system structure and operability through electromechanical features. The bespoke mechanical super-structure resembles a large XY Plotter. This system does not require any surface treatment or preparation as the antenna never touches the surface with the lift being about 50mm.

Sensor Protection:

The Subsurface Radar Unit comprises a monostatic 1GHz Zond radar antenna, the Zond 12e Advanced Radar Controller and a Windows Slave PC running Prism2 measurement capture software. The Zond antenna is self-contained and protected.

Coupling and Attachment:

The Modular Operating Platform also includes the Power Unit and electrical housings for the onboard electrical systems, which enable the measurement and control equipment to function. There is a requirement for mains power provision which is available at all prospective inspection sites. However, contingencies for a primary Power Unit utilising a rechargeable battery array are being considered, with the option for a battery bypass input to enable the apparatus to be directly run of mains electric, if available onsite. Under current design plans, to power all constitute electrical systems, the Power Unit will supply:

- UK/EU mains 220-249V 50Hz AC power;

- 48VDC@10A;
- 12VDC@3A, and
- 5VDC@3A.

The Modular Operating Platform is moved into position for scanning on a lock wall by a crane that needs to be capable of lifting 300kg at the distance from the locations the crane can access and operate from, to the scanning locations.

Routing and Placement:

The super-structure houses the automated Positioning Unit which consists of drive mechanisms, limit mechanical microswitches, 1000ppr rotary encoders and stepper motor controllers.

Technical Requirements:

Temperature and Pressure Rating: Subsurface inspection system operates between -20°C to 60°C internal temperature, while the pressure is not relevant considering the operating environment, i.e. in air at typical atmospheric pressures at or near sea level.

Signal Transmission:

Configuration and interfacing of the Geolocation Unit and Subsurface Radar Unit requires preliminary testing of hardware setup and network connections between the zBELL RTK GNSS geolocation antenna and Zond 12e Advanced Radar Controller to ensure effective communication between both elements during data acquisition.

Test method and steps

The initial testing campaign carried out, so far, with the SIR technology was carried on and around an inland waterway lock operated by VNF on the river Seine. These tests were carried out between 2nd and 5th of December 2025, and the focus was on data collection with the processing of the data taking place at a later date, away from the lock site. The programme of data collection tests was as follows:

- On the 1st of December the SIR modular platform was assembled close the lock to be scanned, and commissioning tests of the assembled equipment carried out (without scanning a structure).
- On the 2nd to 4th of December, the SIR modular platform was placed alongside the vertical lock chamber wall at five separate locations of the northern wall of the lock, towards the Western end by a crane (as shown in Figure 13), and scans of those locations carried out.
- On the 5th of December, the radar antenna was dismantled from the positioning frame and installed in a manual pushcart for the scanning of the horizontal area of ground Northwest of the lock (as shown in Figure 14).

Further details of the implementation of the SIR technology in the pilot test environment are reported in Deliverable D6.2.

- Details of inspected asset (lock, lock location, main known lock specifications, walls and/or areas inspected inc. their location, etc.); documented through descriptions, drawings, photos, etc., as appropriate.
- Test results, comprising:
 - o Details of quadrants and/or specific areas in quadrants where features of interest (Fols) were identified
 - o Details on identified Fols, including qualitative assessment of their characteristics and significance; documented through relevant photos (2D slices and 3D volumes) and associated description, comments, etc.

b) **Data collected**

During the on-site tests, the main data collected was the radar return data captured during the scanning process. This data was recorded in files of the specific format used by the software controlling the radar antenna scans, with a file being recorded for each passage of the antenna (line scan) across the inspected surface. These files also capture GNSS data on the location of the antenna during the scan that can be used to localise the scan results.

In addition to the numerical scan values, other data about the scanning process was recorded, such as the location and stage in the scanning process that each file generated corresponded to, observations about the implementation of the scanning process, and photographic and video records of the scanning.

During the scanning process, each the scan results files generated were checked by visual observation of a simple graphical representation of the scan results in real time, and by checking that a valid file was generated for each passage of the antenna across the scanned area.

The visual observation of the simple graphical representation of the scan results was not used to identify features, it was only viewed and checked to ensure that the output from the antenna was consistent with the scanning process was functioning.

c) **Data processing**

The scanning data captured requires extensive processing to turn the raw numerical values into meaningful results and generate visual media that can be assessed and interpreted for the purposes of obtaining information about the condition of the infrastructure asset that was scanned. The processing and analysis of the scanning data includes the following steps:

- Pre-processing as required (e.g., re-define and/or refine localisation of scans, time zero corrections, filtering and data cleaning, etc.)
- Set-up of processing parameters
- Process of data gathered per specific areas or quadrants through specialised algorithms and codes
- Primary analysis of outputs and extraction of relevant data (in relation to identified Figures of Interests: Fols)
- Specialised analysis and interpretation of data, to produce conclusions and recommendations for end-users and/or entities in charge of maintenance

Figure 15 Example processed SIR data Results from Q2 (a) and A4 (b)

Figure 16 SIR Data workflow

d) Functionality performance summary and details

Table 13 Functionality performance for SIR

Test ID	Functionality	Test description	Expected outcome	Actual Outcome	Status	Remarks / cause if failure
T01	F1-4	The inspection system shall provide the end-user (IM) with the necessary data for making appropriate decision in response to potential risks associated with inspection results.	Data and information related to detected Fols (F1), including indications of the location (F3), size and shape (F2) of Fols, including in visual format (F4), so that the end user may make informed decisions on the criticality of the Fol, and know the location of it.	Fols detected, information (including in visual format) allows size and shape to be estimated, and location determined.	Successful (unverified due to lack of physical evidence)	Actual characteristics of Fols (existence, size, shape, and location) are unknown at this stage, there is no conclusive alternative physical evidence.
T02	F1, F2	The returned processed data from a	Fols of at least 100mm in both axis	Fols with characteristic dimensions of	This was successfully verified	There was no conclusive physical

		scan shall have sufficient resolution to enable the majority of significant defect to be identified.	perpendicular to the direction of the radar emission should be detected by the SIR system and correctly identified and scaled as such.	approximately 100mm were detected.	in laboratory, but partially successful on site (unverified due to lack of physical evidence)	evidence to allow comparison of detected size of FoI vs. actual size.
T03	F1, F2	Features, within the required resolution limits, will be reliably detected and identified in the returned processed data.	Not less than 80% of the Fols in the locations scanned larger than the limits should be detected and correctly identified and scaled.	Processed results showed relevant variation in FoI detection for different Quadrants and areas.	Partially successful (unverified due to lack of physical evidence)	There was no conclusive physical evidence to allow comparison of detected size of FoI vs. actual size.
T04	F2, F4	The system should be able to discriminate between and classify features in terms of their material composition.	The regions of FoI composed of different material classes greater than 100mm in size should be identified as being of different material classes. Also, the assignment of material type label for all FoI should be correct for 80% of features.	Classification of Fols by distinct material types from results collected in CRISTAL was not achieved.	Not achieved	Classification of Fols into distinct material types is still cutting-edge scientific area of research, it requires large volume of data to achieve necessary experience for expert interpretation. Further R&D is required to achieve this capability.
T05	F3	The accuracy of the	The position of a FoI given	Position of detected FoI	Partially successful	There was no conclusive

		positional data component of the scan data shall be sufficient to enable any features identified in the scans to be located on the physical structure.	by scan data should be accurate to within ± 1 m of the actual position of the Fol relative to the reference point for the whole structure.	can be related to location on, around, or within the structure within ± 1 m	(unverified due to lack of physical evidence).	physical evidence to allow comparison of detected Fols location with actual physical location.
T06	F2	The size characteristics determined by the system for the features detected and identified shall be accurate	The identified volume of Fol should be accurate to within $\pm 50\%$ of the actual volume of the Fol	Volume of detected Fols has been estimated from results.	Partially successful (unverified due to lack of physical evidence)	There was no conclusive physical evidence to allow comparison of detected volume of Fol vs. actual volume.
T07	F1-7	The radar scanning process shall enable features to be detected, at the required accuracy and resolution, at a sufficient depth below the surface of the structure to detect the most common types of significant defects	Fols at between 1-3m behind the external surface of the structure should be detected and identified (within the accuracy limits specified above)	Fols up to 1m behind the external surface of lock walls, and up to 2.5m below area of ground surface detected, with uncertain accuracy.	Partially successful (unverified)	The compromise between depth/distance and resolution was biased towards ability to detect and characterise Fols; increased distance/depth could be achieved with lower resolution, depending on priorities.

e) Conclusions on results analysis

The data acquisition phase of the test has been completed, but the final processing and interpretation are still ongoing. Specifically, the identification and differentiation of subsurface material layers requires a larger volume of data to achieve the necessary experience by the involvement of geotechnical experts; this could be done through different methods, e.g., machine-learning may be an effective tool. The

complexity of the data collected, particularly the analysis of signal behaviour to distinguish between layers, goes beyond standard processing capabilities and necessitates specialized expertise to yield reliable and operationally relevant results.

From a methodological standpoint, the test strategy proved effective in gathering the necessary data, However a key challenge faced by the verification and further validation of test results was the lack of information regarding physical evidence of asset design/structure and its condition (i.e., existence and characteristics of defects or features that were identified as Fols, their location, etc.), which is essential to compare the results with. Such information could be acquired through invasive inspection methods, which were not feasible to be applied on lock walls and surrounding ground, in the context of the CRISTAL project.

f) **Impact assessment**

Although full interpretation of the results is still pending, the expected operational impact of this solution is significant. Once the data is fully processed and material layers can be reliably identified, this technology could support the implementation of predictive maintenance strategies for inland waterway infrastructure. By providing precise, non-invasive insights into the condition of substructures, the solution may help detect early signs of degradation, optimise maintenance interventions, and reduce overall maintenance costs.

In its current state, the system has demonstrated technical feasibility in terms of data collection and initial processing, which validates its potential. However, until full interpretation is achieved, the impact remains prospective. The continued involvement of geotechnical experts and a structured plan for data exploitation are key to unlocking this potential and translating it into operational value for infrastructure managers.

Synchromodal Corridor Management System (CERTH)

a) **Operating characteristics**

Environmental requirements

SCMS is a digital system (platform) installed in servers located in CERTH premises, therefore, there are no special environmental requirements regarding the pilot (river) area.

Test method and steps

The system setup is already in place with all its functionalities developed.

Data has been provided on water depth and lock availability for testing the SCMS ability to leverage data from the DT's API and retrieve information from EURIS to operate the alert system and also the disruption impact estimation and rerouting functionality. In addition, the system has KPIs (such as the number of alerts received every day) for evaluating its operation.

Test reports and documentation

The initial system description is available in D3.1 - Specifications on synchromodal transport management systems, components and services. The SCMS documentation and test reports are to be delivered at the end of the project.

b) Functionality performance summary and details

The SCMS is available on the website <https://scms-demo.imet.gr/>

Figure 17 Home page of the SCMS platform

The alert system is operational. However, the digital twin does not produce prospective data on the duration of alerts, and they do not have port data to assess potential congestion, which would allow for a better assessment of the impact of a broken lock and the bottlenecks.

The disruption impact estimation and multimodal rerouting system are operational and allow for estimating rerouting time by road in connection with Google Maps, as well as identifying the nearest river port for loading/unloading cargo. However, rail inter-modality is not fully addressed, as today it is practically impossible for the railway system to have high responsiveness to demand changes.

The observatory is developed in order to receive data once the connection to the DT is fully established; it needs data to create a competitive advantage over EURIS, particularly forecasting data about the future.

c) Conclusions on results analysis

The tests are still ongoing; the final report will be submitted at the end of the project. At this stage, it is mainly the prediction data from the DT that is missing.

d) **Impact assessment**

The SCMS (Synchromodal Corridor Management System) has demonstrated the feasibility of consolidating multimodal transport status information into a unified platform. Through its integration with the Digital Twin and external data sources (EURIS, Google Maps), the system provides a foundation for real-time alerts, disruption impact estimation, and re-routing of inland waterway cargo flows.

In its current state, the SCMS offers operational added value for barge operators, logistics providers, and infrastructure managers by:

- Enabling alert reception and real-time response to disruptions
- Allowing route feasibility assessment based on both current and forecasted conditions
- Supporting river-road synchromodal re-routing in case of infrastructure failure (e.g. broken locks)

However, several limitations reduce the system's immediate impact:

- The Digital Twin does not yet provide prospective data on alert duration
- Port congestion data is not integrated, reducing the accuracy of rerouting assessments
- Rail mode integration is limited due to structural constraints in the rail sector
- The observatory component lacks real-time data to fully differentiate it from existing platforms like EURIS

Despite these limitations, the SCMS lays important groundwork for improving inland waterway reliability. Once full integration with the Digital Twin is achieved and forecasting data becomes operational, the platform could significantly support modal shift toward inland navigation by increasing transparency, predictability, and responsiveness within logistics chains. Additionally, SCMS's observatory functionality holds potential to inform public administration and infrastructure planning, particularly if enriched with analytics on infrastructure reliability and navigability.

Acoustic Emissions (CERTH)

a) **Operating characteristics**

Environment requirements

During installation the waves must not be excessive, and in case of heavy rain the AE logger must be enclosed into IP67 box, the AE logger is by itself IP65 which is dust and wind proof as well as light rain proof.

Test method and steps

The technology was tested twice on the river Saône, each time on the same lock, first in June 2023 and second in June 2024, for one day each time.

Measurement/Assessment	Additional details/ description	Test Measurands/Metrics	KPI definition (if any)
Sensitivity of acoustic detection	Measured sensitivity to detect signals > 20 dB.	Signal strength (dB)	Detect emissions > 20 dB against background noise at <1ms latency.
Sensor scalability	Ability to deploy many AE logger at the same time and ability of the system to parse parallel such recordings.	Number of loggers and sensors per logger deployed	Sensor scalability
Kind of failure defects	Detecting metal microcracks before major metal crack failures and detecting upcoming out of the normal operation failures (by positioning sensors close to gate parts under inspection various kind of failures can be detected, e.g. near pistons or at the bottom of the gate buildup of canal precipitations)	Sensors applicability to various sources of defects	Kinds of gates failures
Minimum disruption of waterlock's operational	Minimum disruption to overall waterlock's gates allowing the passage of ships during inspection	Testing gate's smooth operability during AE recording.	Minimum waterlock's operational disruption

<p>The operation of the inspection system must not provide an unacceptable risk to the general public, employees, property, or environment.</p>	<p>The operation of the inspection system cannot completely eliminate all dangers to the environment, property, employees, and the general public. However, by taking the right precautions when installing the sensors and turning on the AE logger, such hazards should be reduced. Any danger resides during the installation of the sensors not during operation.</p>	<p>Reporting the possible points of danger during installation and operation and evaluating the level of danger.</p>	
<p>System logging and timestamping</p>	<p>Real-time logging under operational conditions.</p>	<p>Percentage of events logged (%)</p>	<p>99.9% of events logged.</p>
<p>Localization accuracy</p>	<p>Accuracy of pinpointing emission source.</p>	<p>Error radius (m)</p>	<p>Localization microcrack error prediction <0.5m. Localization impact detection error <2.5m.</p>
<p>Output failure assessment report</p>	<p>Providing constant assessments from streaming input AE recordings.</p>	<p>Ability to enumerate all of the outputs</p>	

Table 14 Test method and steps for acoustic emissions

Test reports and documentation

All test and reports will be included into D10.1 and D2.3 deliverable.

b) Data collected

- Regarding the microcrack detection model laboratory PLB and on pilot site PLB were collected and added with various amplitude augmentations to the Normal Operating Signal as recorded during the pilot operations. This constitutes the reference point for the neural to train in detection.
- Regarding the deviation from Normal Operating Space abnormal operations of the gate were recorded and also augmented to simulate general failure schemes of the gate, with impulse hammer recordings. As reference a NOS (normal operating signal) was used and tested against the abnormal operations.
- The signals were recorded using 4096 slots of recording using 2Mega samples per second with filters starting from 1kHz up to 150kHz.
- The produced data stored in the DT are the following two vectors the ["OPV-indices", "OPVavg"] and the ["micro-crack-prediction"].

c) Data processing

This report concludes to sample vector

--- Model detecting outliers on normal operating space:

"OPV-indices": [4.153889304397582, 13.97079102298917, 18.817003724266467, 12.978324698338518, 8.86068740363236, 22.425944508023175, 14.29487268954278, 13.468515359249778, 18.048799152130396, 3.1788705357635605, 6.67099996245956, 17.052113041924915, 13.532000722741921, 1.6922385769764634, 10.261317497515506, 28.781735803698325, 42.31049147353487, 56.61060925413544, 24.785079781754714, 18.620653171021374, 15.621445207447861, 82.44024957421551, 17.390877209053862, 6.4757873744370436, 15.568178961343131, 19.98649098305784, 18.94637506771568], "OPVavg": 19.51645711338399,

"OPV-indices" these are 27 constituents detecting various profile constituents building the Outlier Profile Vector (OPV) it is in percentage of difference in relation to a reference OPV which we consider good operation of the system.

"OPVavg": is the average percentage

Detection occurs if differences (high percentages) are consistent during various samples then this indicates a clear deviation from the normal operation. It can catch various mechanisms of failure depending also on where we place the sensors across the gate

--- Model detecting build-up of microcracks near sensor:

“micro-crack-prediction”: 0.3

Detects micro-crack patterns near the sensor: if near zero then no micro-crack patterns is detected, if near one then microcrack has been detected. A history with persistent elevated or bursts of near one values is an indication of build-up micro-cracks which may lead to metallic crack.

d) Functionality performance summary and details

Test ID	Functionality	Test description	Expected outcome	Actual Outcome	Status	Remarks / cause if failure
T0001	The system shall detect acoustic emissions related to structural anomalies.	External AE generator producing AE with variable amplitude and testing its ability to detect PZT outputs of only 1 μ V.	Detect emissions > 20 dB against background noise at <1ms latency.		Passed	
T0002	The system shall localize the source of emissions on the gate surface.	PLB tests and impulse hammer tests		Localization microcrack error prediction <0.5m. Localization impact (100-500 newton) detection error <2.5m.	passed	
T0003	The system shall log and timestamp acoustic events for post-analysis.	Producing a single hit with the AE generator and checking the timestamp of recording			passed	
T0004	Scalability on the number of pzt sensors across the	Ability of multiple micro-SHM to wirelessly			passed	

	water-lock gate	connect to the AEwin software logger for in parallel AE recordings				
T0005	Detecting metal microcracks before major metal crack failures and detecting upcoming out of the normal operation failures.	Testing the ability to detect micro-cracks patterns among gate's normal operation. The confidence level of a micro-crack is between 0.0 -1.0		88% accuracy of the autoencoder	passed	
T0006	The inspection system shall provide the end-user with the necessary assessment data for making appropriate decision in response to upcoming failures in the gate	The library produces a percentage of deviation between a reference recording of gate's normal operation and the currently recording under inspection. The higher and persistent output indicates a high outlier gate operation		Outlier Profile Vector constituents and confidence on microcrack.	passed	

Table 15 Functionality performance for acoustic emissions

e) **Conclusions on results analysis and Testing Methodology**

The acoustic emissions (AE) monitoring system delivered strong performance across all test criteria and confirms its relevance for the predictive maintenance of inland waterway infrastructure. All test objectives were successfully achieved, and no critical technical failures were reported during the trials. The following key performance indicators were validated:

- Detection of emissions above 20 dB against background noise with <1 ms latency;
- Localization of microcrack sources with accuracy <0.5 m, and impact detection accuracy <2.5 m;
- Real-time logging of 99.9% of acoustic events;
- Sensor and logger scalability, enabling parallel deployments;
- Applicability to various gate components and defect types.

The system enables detection of microcrack formations prior to the development of major structural failures. Additionally, it can identify abnormal mechanical behaviours or deviations from normal gate operation through the “Outlier Profile Vector” (OPV) and microcrack prediction models. These features provide a solid technical basis for an early warning capability.

The proposed operational model recommends inspections every 4–6 months, using sensors left in place and only reconnecting them to a power source and logging unit during periodic campaigns. This approach minimizes operational disruption while allowing regular condition assessment.

However, several practical limitations were identified during testing, highlighting areas for future improvement:

- Acoustic coupling issues can reduce signal transmission quality. This can be mitigated through improved sensor holders with integrated greasing or by re-installing sensors during each inspection.
- Limited Wi-Fi connectivity between AE loggers and the AEWIn software may impair real-time operation. Deployment of Wi-Fi extenders is suggested to ensure robust communication.
- The system’s ability to support long-term predictive maintenance planning (e.g., anticipating failures weeks in advance) remains to be validated in real operational conditions. More field experience is needed to fully exploit this potential. This is addressed by the latest measurements and additional failures simulation AE measurements taken from the last visit in the Italian pilot recorded during the last visit at summer of 2025. Further on that will be displayed in 5.2 deliverable.

In summary, the AE system functions reliably and delivers valuable diagnostic data, but its application in a continuous predictive maintenance context will require operational refinement and further validation in live infrastructure monitoring programs.

- f) **Impact assessment** on KPI’s, relevant or irrelevant functionalities to improve viability, maintenance and modal shift

The acoustic emissions (AE) monitoring system tested in the CRISTAL project offers a promising and technically mature solution to support the predictive maintenance of inland waterway infrastructure. Its ability to detect microcracks and other structural anomalies early, through highly accurate signal detection and localization, demonstrates real potential to reduce unplanned interventions, extend asset life, and improve infrastructure reliability. In particular, the system addresses several key operational needs:

- Early warning capability for structural degradation, enabling maintenance teams to act before failures occur.
- Low-disruption deployment, with sensors that can remain in place and be periodically activated, minimizing operational interference.
- Scalability, allowing the technology to be extended across multiple gates and structures without significant additional cost or complexity.

Its integration into maintenance routines, such as biannual inspections, would provide infrastructure managers like VNF with objective, sensor-based indicators to complement visual inspections. Over time, the system could also contribute to data-driven maintenance planning, building historical baselines and detecting trends in asset behaviour.

However, full integration into predictive maintenance workflows will require additional operational experience. Tests have shown that AE sensors work well within a 1-meter range when placed near points of interest. However, large-scale deployment requires further refinement of the definition of points of interest and how this can be translated into a simple guideline. Improving real-time communication (e.g., through Wi-Fi extenders) is also an important consideration for large-scale deployment, although this issue falls more broadly under wireless connectivity rather than the AE method itself. Regarding the definition of clear intervention thresholds, the method relies downstream on the visual recognition of simple patterns based on percentage deviations from historical data. However, this knowledge must be acquired during system operation and is specific to each waterlock. Although it doesn't require advanced technical skills, the digital twin operator must still develop a basic ability to distinguish patterns based on historical percentage deviations from normal operation, with the system serving as an amplifier for these subtle changes. This is especially true when failures arise from causes other than metallic microcracking. In the case of microcracks, their physical generation patterns are more specific, making them relatively easy to detect. By definition, predictive maintenance on large dynamic systems requires the operator to develop a basic heuristic ability, with the detection system enhancing deviations and pattern recognition to support the operator.

Overall, the impact of this technology lies in its capacity to shift maintenance strategies from reactive to predictive, increasing the reliability of inland navigation infrastructure and supporting the broader modal shift objectives of the CRISTAL project.

Digital Twin (Fraunhofer)

a) Operating characteristics

Environment requirements

REST API; Websocket; NGINX web server. For the development Angular is used.

The environment requirements are described in D5.1: Technical Concept of a Digital Twin.

Test method and steps

The Digital twin of Lock and Digital twin of buoys could be tested in the French pilot.

Only a few data collected on the French pilot about buoys, but the combination with the Polish pilot's data made it possible to test the digital twin of smart buoys.

Data from acoustic emission sensor tests were transmitted to the digital twin to provide input to the DT Lock.

The following illustration below (figure 18) reflects the development and deployment status of the digital twin components as of April 2025.

Figure 18 Status of digital twin's test for French pilot

Use-Case French Overview for French Pilot

Use-Case ID	Name	Priority	Status
F-1	Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR) Technology	Must	It is currently possible to display example data. First processed data seems to be available (15.04.)
F-2	Acoustic Emission (AE) System	Must	First data is available
F-3	Alert System - Lock Door Mechanisms	Must	Currently under development
F-4	Lock Chamber Dimensions	Should	Done
F-5	General Lock Status	Could	Done
F-6	Alert System - General Lock Status	Could	Done
F-7	General Information Indicators	Could	Done
F-8	Documents	Could	Done
F-9	Buoys	Could	Done
F-10	Alert System – Buoys	Could	Done

b) Data collected

DT of locks: VNF sent data on the maintenance schedule and lock closure schedule.

Figure 19 Maintenance dashboard

The mobilization of AE and SIR data for maintenance is not yet fully operational.

For AE, a few data were received in April 2025 that they can use to make analysis and send this data to the SCMS. The feature is about 70% complete.

The most complicated part is SIR: the functionalities and the front end have been defined, but the data has not been shared. Only rough data has been received, no processed data.

DT of buoys: GPS position data

c) **Data processing**

The alert feature regarding the maintenance status and lock closures addressed to the SCMS was designed.

d) **Detailed results**

Figure 20 Detailed DT Lock test status

DT Lock

Brief summary

Origin (DS.1 ID)	Name	Priority	Status	Country
Main point DS.1	Recognizability of the navigability of the lock	Must	Done	
REQ-FU-FR-13,14 REQ-FU-IT-31,32	Provide a Smart Monitor GUI to display lock related documents	Could	Done	
REQ-FU-FR-4,7,8,9,11 REQ-FU-IT-21,25,26,27,29	Provide a Smart Monitor GUI for visual representation of the lock and related information indicators	Must	Done – real data and example data	
REQ-FU-FR-1	Integration and visualization of the SIR data	Must	It is currently possible to display example data. First processed data seems to be available (15.04.)	
REQ-FU-FR-2,3,5,6 REQ-FU-IT-18,19,22,23 REQ-FU-CM-6	Integration and visualization of AE data	Must	First data is available	
REQ-FU-CM-7	Maintenance and failure categories are linked to downtime from a static table	Should	Done	
REQ-FU-FR-10, REQ-FU-IT-28	Endpoints for accessing pilots' data as well as alert for users on general lock status	Must / Could	Done	
REQ-NFU-FR-1 REQ-NFU-IT-1 REQ-NFU-GE-1-27	Security and user management	Must	The DB is secured (not encrypted)	
REQ-FU-FR-19	Real-time data out of EURIS	Won't Have	Done - Data can be transferred asynchronously from EURIS	

Figure 21 Detailed DT Buoy test status

DT Buoy

Brief summary

Origin (DS.1 ID)	Name	Priority	Status	Country
REQ-FU-FR-15 REQ-FU-PO-1	Acquire buoy data	Must	Data is from the past, no GPS data from France	
REQ-FU-FR-16 REQ-FU-PO-2,3	Provide a Smart Monitor	Must	Done	
REQ-FU-PO-5,6,7,8 REQ-FU-CM-5	Provide an alert system for water level, ice cover thickness and ship class data	Must	Done	
REQ-FU-FR-17 VNF	Provide an alert system for buoy positions	Must	Done	
REQ-NFU-GE-1-12	Provide security and user management	Must	The DB is secured (not encrypted)	
REQ-NFU-PO-1	Calculate river condition	Could	Checked but not enough data available	
REQ-FU-PO-4 REQ-FU-CM-4	Provide predictions on buoy data and navigability	Could	Checked but not enough data available	

e) Conclusion on functionalities

The framework of the digital twin of locks and buoys was implemented although all the necessary data for the development of the global model do not yet have the required level of precision.

The prediction functionality has not yet been established for the DT of locks and smart buoys.

f) Critical analysis of the testing methodology

There is a lack of real-time technologies and of historical data to provide relevant data to the DT for analysis and prediction.

Even if the DTs had received interpreted data, the duration of the project would not have allowed them to establish long-term statistics sufficient to implement machine learning and make medium- to long-term predictions about the state of the locks. This could potentially be the subject of a future research project, ideally involving another expertise to ensure the interpretation of the rough data provided by the SIR.

g) Impact assessment

The Digital Twin (DT) framework developed for locks and smart buoys represents an important step toward digitizing the monitoring and predictive maintenance of inland waterway infrastructure. The integration of real-time and scheduled data (e.g., lock closures, maintenance planning) into a central system lays the foundation for improved situational awareness and coordination with other systems such as the SCMS. In its current state, the DT provides partial functionality:

- It is structurally in place, with the web-based architecture and system interface developed and operational.
- Initial data integration, particularly for locks, is underway, including maintenance schedules and limited acoustic emission data.

- For smart buoys, GPS data was collected and used in combination with Polish pilot data to enable testing and simulation.

However, the full potential of the DT remains unrealized due to two main constraints:

1. Insufficient precision and volume of incoming data, especially from the SIR system, where only unprocessed, rough data was shared.
2. Lack of long-term historical datasets, limiting the ability to train models for prediction and proactive maintenance.

Despite these limitations, the digital twin provides a valuable framework that can scale and mature with time. It holds significant long-term potential to:

- Enable condition-based maintenance by centralizing data from diverse monitoring systems (AE, SIR, SCMS)
- Support future predictive analytics, once historical datasets are established
- Improve responsiveness to disruptions by aligning infrastructure status with logistics coordination platforms

Although not fully operational during the CRISTAL project, the DT can serve as a core digital infrastructure for VNF and partner organisations. With further development, particularly around real-time data flows and analytics, the Digital Twin could contribute meaningfully to modal shift objectives by increasing infrastructure reliability, enabling proactive maintenance, and enhancing coordination between stakeholders.

4. Impact assessment of French inland waterways pilot solutions

This section aims to identify the impacts of the seven technologies tested as part of the French pilot. To do so, VNF organized three living labs with VNF users (carriers, clients, tourism professionals) and VNF managers of maintenance and works. It allowed the identification of the most relevant functionalities to support the goals of improving the resilience of inland waterway transport and increasing modal shift.

This section presents the impact assessment of each technology, the conditions needed to foster their acceptance by the end users, and the KPIs achieved by these technologies.

Objectives of the CRISTAL project: to increase the modal share of river freight by 20% and its reliability by 80%

In terms of ton-kilometres, large-scale inland waterway transport (IWT) is the most cost-effective mode of transport.

It is a safe and reliable option, with low rates of theft and accidents, and it emits relatively low greenhouse gases while offering minimal congestion risk (CCNR, Market Insight 2023; European Commission, NAIADES III Action Plan). For these reasons, it has strong potential to support modal shift objectives.

Despite these advantages, IWT is often perceived as complex. Many forwarders are unfamiliar with its operation, and surveys conducted by VNF indicate that some users consider the infrastructure to be outdated and maintenance to be slow (CRISTAL D8.1 – French RP Specification and Baseline Measurements. May 2024). In response, VNF has contributed to several initiatives designed to simplify and improve the network's usability and efficiency, such as EURIS and NAVI, tools providing real-time information on navigation conditions and infrastructure status. The CRISTAL project is an extension of this effort, aiming to strengthen the attractiveness and operational reliability of inland waterway freight transport.

CRISTAL focuses on both technological innovation and digitalization, advancing the principles of the Physical Internet, and offering governance solutions and business models. It targets two main areas

- Resilient infrastructure, by developing intelligent structural health monitoring systems that enable both preventive and predictive maintenance. These smart systems can identify deteriorating conditions, anticipate failures, and signal the need for intervention, ultimately contributing to extended asset lifespans and improved availability.
- Resilient navigation, through the development of real-time alert and forecasting systems for water levels and hydrological conditions, thereby enhancing decision-making capabilities and ensuring continued navigability under variable environmental conditions.

The overall objectives of the CRISTAL project are to increase the modal share of inland waterway freight by 20%, to improve its reliability by 80%, and to ensure 50% transport capacity during extreme weather

events. Achieving these goals relies on a set of innovative solutions combining real-time monitoring, predictive maintenance, digital corridor management, and simplified administrative processes.

To better illustrate how these technologies support the project's strategic goals, the following table maps each solution tested in CRISTAL to its intended contributions:

Table 16 Contribution of CRISTAL Technologies to Strategic Objectives

Technology Feature	Description / Functionality	Linked CRISTAL Strategic Objectives
CEDRE	Electronic freight documentation tool and API system to automate and simplify declarations, enabling multimodal planning and reducing empty runs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase modal share (+20%) • Digitisation of logistics processes • Improved efficiency and attractiveness of IWT for shippers
Fluv'IOTe	IoT-based tracking of barge position and quay occupancy using AIS and image data; predictive model to assess barge deposits/retrievals.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased operational reliability • Better quay usage visibility • Supports infrastructure capacity optimisation
Smart Buoys	Solar-powered buoys with GNSS modules to monitor water levels and position; tested in non-navigated and partially navigated areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real-time water condition monitoring • Support for 50% capacity goal under extreme weather • Enhanced navigability and safety
Acoustic Emission Sensors (AE)	Real-time detection of microcracks in lock gates; localisation accuracy <0.5 m; predictive failure alerts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enables predictive maintenance • Improves infrastructure reliability • Reduces unplanned closures
Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR)	Ground-penetrating radar to detect underground structural conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complements AE in diagnostics • Strengthens planning for preventive maintenance • Supports long-term infrastructure resilience
Synchromodal Corridor Management System (SCMS)	Digital platform integrating alert data, lock status, and rerouting logic; supports multimodal freight coordination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintains continuity of freight flows during disruptions • Improves coordination and contingency planning • Foundational for resilient corridor operations

Digital Twin (DT)	Web-based integration of AE, SIR, lock, and buoy data to form a virtual model of the infrastructure; currently under development	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Centralises real-time and predictive data• Interfaces with SCMS for enhanced corridor management• Potential for long-term trend analysis and predictive operations
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Impacts of the innovations tested to achieve these objectives

This section analyses the impacts of the CRISTAL innovations in light of the project’s strategic objectives: increasing the modal share of inland waterway transport, improving its reliability, and modernizing maintenance practices. The analysis draws from three Living Labs conducted during the project, which gathered input from stakeholders including VNF representatives, barge operators, logistics companies, and infrastructure experts. During these sessions, the expected benefits and possible limitations of each technology were discussed in detail.

The technologies Fluv’IOTe and Smart Buoys were not presented during the Living Labs due to development delays, but VNF teams directly involved in their implementation were interviewed separately to gather targeted feedback.

Each innovation was originally selected to address a specific operational challenge. The table below provides a summary of these initial expectations, a “pre-test memo” of the hoped-for impacts:

Table 17 Initial Objectives and Expected Impacts of Each Tested Technology (Pre-Test Phase)

Technology Feature	Initial Purpose / Problem Addressed	Expected Impact (Pre-Test)
CEDRE	Administrative complexity in freight declaration and limited digitisation of logistics flows.	Simplify and digitalise transport declarations, reduce administrative burden, decrease empty trips through better cargo visibility, support multimodal planning.
Fluv’IOTe	Lack of real-time knowledge on barge positions and quay occupancy.	Improve quay usage visibility, optimise barge movements, reduce waiting times, support modal shift by improving service predictability.
Smart Buoys	Insufficient real-time data on water levels and navigability.	Enable continuous hydrological monitoring, improve alert systems, enhance navigation safety and reliability during extreme weather.
Acoustic Emission Sensors (AE)	Difficulty in detecting early infrastructure degradation.	Identify microcracks in lock gates before failure, enable predictive maintenance, extend infrastructure lifespan, reduce emergency repairs.
Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR)	Limited insight into the substructure condition of infrastructures.	Map material layers and defects, support planning of preventive maintenance, reduce cost and improve safety of inspections.

Synchromodal Corridor Management System (SCMS)	Lack of real-time rerouting and disruption visibility for IWT.	Provide dynamic alerts, disruption impact estimation, and rerouting support to make inland navigation more reliable and competitive.
Digital Twin (DT)	Fragmented infrastructure data, lack of predictive tools.	Centralise data for locks and buoys, enable scenario modelling and predictive maintenance, support better coordination with SCMS and operators.

Summary of Living Labs

Three Living Labs were conducted between October 2024 and April 2025 to explore the anticipated impacts of selected CRISTAL technologies. These interactive sessions brought together internal and external stakeholders to gather feedback on usability, value, adoption potential, and integration challenges.

1. Living Lab 1 – October 9, 2024

Held in Paris during the National Users Committee (CNU) session at VNF headquarters, this session focused on CEDRE (digital freight declaration and load optimization) and SCMS (Synchromodal Corridor Management System). Participants included:

- 29 stakeholders from VNF, freight carriers, leisure boating associations, national logistics and infrastructure bodies (e.g. AUTF, E2F, Agir pour le Fluvial, FFPP, ANPEI, FFCK).
- Three breakout groups (Freight, Leisure, and VNF) debated features, use cases, integration, and business models.
- Discussions targeted integration with existing maintenance systems, real-time alerts, interoperability with external logistics data, and confidence in alert reliability.
- SCMS was perceived as particularly useful for avoiding disruptions, but concerns were raised about multimodal rerouting and the need for alignment with tools like EuRIS.

2. Living Lab 2 – October 15, 2024

Conducted in Paris during the Steering Committee of the Major Works Directorate at VNF headquarters, this session included structural engineers and operational staff from VNF and focused on Acoustic Emission, Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR), and Digital Twins with 12 participants (9 structural engineers, 3 VNF staff)

- Discussions targeted technical features, operational integration within VNF's infrastructure, institutional readiness, economic impact, and alignment with VNF's operational models
- AE was appreciated for early fault detection despite concerns about calibration, noise, and costs; SIR was valued for structural insights with questions on portability and adaptability; Digital Twins were seen as promising but faced challenges in data, IT, and cultural adoption

3. Living Lab 3 – April 16, 2025

Held online, this session focused on Acoustic Emission, Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR), and Digital Twins, with 10 participants (7 VNF maintenance technicians, 3 VNF staff).

- Discussions explored implementation challenges, technical constraints (e.g. noise interference with AE), and potential for predictive diagnostics.
- SIR and AE were appreciated for their contribution to planning, while the Digital Twin concept was viewed as promising for network-level decision support, despite ambiguity around added value beyond sensor data.

Note: The technologies Fluv'IOTe (barge geolocation and quay occupancy) and Smart Buoys (water level sensors) were not presented during the Living Labs due to delays in test deployment and data maturity at the time. Feedback was instead gathered through direct interviews with the technical VNF teams responsible for development and implementation, as described in D8.1.

These participatory workshops helped identify not only the positive potential of the innovations but also barriers to adoption, implementation constraints, and areas where actual results diverged from initial expectations. This input was essential in shaping the conclusions of this deliverable.

The paragraphs that follow evaluate whether these expectations were met based on test results and stakeholder reactions, highlighting both confirmed value and any observed limitations or gaps.

a) CEDRE

The key benefits identified during the living labs for this technology were as follows:

- reduction in administrative paperwork and increased competitiveness.
- smoothing transportation costs thanks to the global view of navigation frequencies and the development of statistics that could help optimize freight routes on waterways. The technology could also enable the search for opportunities for cargo pooling between shippers, provided the materials are compatible, and could potentially help define sites for logistics deployment.

The Freight group participants expect confidentiality regarding the nature of the goods being transported. They also believe that it is necessary to distinguish between information connections for industrial fleets and artisanal fleets, as they do not respond to the same types of needs.

The connection to VELI is considered important, as it provides clear benefits in terms of communication, multimodality, and responsiveness. The positive example of Wallonia's integration with transport management systems was cited.

To avoid empty returns and enable freight exchange, it would be useful to segment the hold into cells to carry multiple types of goods simultaneously.

Several challenges were identified for implementation:

- Convincing data providers to share necessary data.
- While the technology offers a connection to Transport Management Systems (TMS), many large shippers, especially in bulk construction transport, do not have such systems. There may also be interoperability issues between existing TMS and the CEDRE technology.
- The Freight group participants find the administrative workload for transporters to be inconsistent and redundant, and it would be preferable to avoid multiplying interfaces for inland waterway and port information transmission. Harmonizing these would reduce the number of declarations.
- It was considered interesting if an intermediary used the data to identify regular trips and launch new routes; for the Freight group, the data could feed into a system like AI Cargo.

In conclusion, according to VNF, navigators are in favour of the idea of reducing administrative formalities but are cautious about the empty return functionality, as they are used to being assigned transport missions by the charterer.

The overall view of navigation frequency should allow charterers to smooth their transport costs by using more river freight, which is less expensive than road transport.

The client is not concerned with the data collection methods but may be interested in limiting empty returns in order to reduce costs.

Some inland waterway carriers are opposed to the empty return functionality, as it impacts their revenue, and their interest towards administrative simplification is limited because it requires them to finance modifications to their TMS. Although, some of them like CFT and Cemex decided to implement this technology and connect it to their TMS. One of the challenges in generalizing the limitation of empty returns is that, out of the tens of thousands of trips made each year in France, most are performed on a time basis. Returning with a second cargo wastes time and requires renegotiating contracts with shippers, something inland waterway carriers are unwilling to do in order to avoid jeopardizing their commercial relationships.

The statistical data on the goods transported is available on open data platforms, although some are privatized. They are used by shippers to generate statistics on dock activity. These data are also sold to CNR and Haropa, which provides a discount to lessees on their fees when goods are shipped or received via inland waterways. This generates for VNF revenue of around €100,000 per year. A review is underway regarding the overhaul of the freight transport fee, as the current scale is very old, established in the 1990s. Measured in tons/kilometres, it could evaluate, as e-commerce is growing.

The goal is to optimize revenue while supporting the competitiveness of inland waterway traffic. A calculation of freight tolls on 130 transport routes is currently being carried out to establish a new scale. The acquisition of more precise data on transport through the development of CEDRE would help to enhance the reliability of this data and the revenue from this toll.

b) Fluv'IOTe

The Fluv'IOTe project was initiated in response to operational needs expressed by users such as Cemex and Sogestran, who sought more accurate geolocation of barges and the ability to detect mooring line failures. In practice, CFT and Cemex are now equipping their barges with geolocation systems. However, the transmission of this data to VNF is not yet implemented, limiting its use for broader operational optimisation or integration into systems such as CEDRE. Currently, EuRIS has the capability to calculate dock occupancy using barge geolocation data transmitted via VNF, but the lack of available real-time data has prevented this functionality from being fully utilised. Yet, for modal shift to be viable and competitive, it is essential to know quay occupancy rates to optimise routing, reduce waiting times, and match the reliability and predictability of road transport.

Despite these limitations, the Fluv'IOTe pilot delivered concrete positive results. The system successfully combined AIS data with high-resolution imagery to detect barge deposits, retrievals, and pass-throughs, achieving an estimated 85% accuracy on labelled validation samples. The pilot test conducted at the Louis Blériot quay in Paris showed that it is feasible to forecast quay occupancy and better understand barge movement behaviour. These capabilities support both real-time decision-making and long-term planning. Additionally, the technology holds significant potential if connected with operational tools such as CEDRE or the SCMS, offering a clearer picture of port activity and improving reliability across the inland waterway freight chain.

c) French Smart Buoys

The goal of the buoys is to define the navigable channel within the river, distinguishing it from the rocky bottoms / sandbanks, and to allow ships to navigate within it while avoiding obstacles.

The flood period occurs from November to May, primarily in the spring. The increase in flow is rapid. During the flood period, the buoys often move out of their intended position defining the navigable channel. On average, 2-3 buoys are displaced per flood, 1 to 5 times a year.

In such cases, maintenance technicians must form two teams that walk along the entire Moselle to identify the displaced buoys; they then visit the sites of the displaced buoys on the Moselle by boat to reposition them correctly. This takes a total of two days.

The displacement alert eliminates the need to send out a verification team after each flood, providing immediate notifications to quickly warn waterway users of potential danger.

The illuminated signage ensures safe navigation during the night.

The main potential impacts of this technology are to reduce accidents for ships in the event of an unexpected interruption in channel indication by the buoys and to minimize maintenance time. Ultimately, the goal would not be to equip all the buoys, but rather those that are most critical in terms of flood risk. In the Saône and Rhône rivers, lights are mounted on piles, preventing their displacement. The Moselle, Seine, and Loire rivers, on the other hand, have buoys.

d) SIR Technology

The benefits perceived by the structural engineers for this technology were:

- Detection of unseen damage
- Reduction in the number of necessary underwater inspections
- Tool to size work, particularly during the pre-project phase (likely more accurate than core samples by geotechnical design offices)
- More detailed 3D images than other inspection methods
- Reduction of risk and thus costs (limiting additional work and overruns due to insufficient initial diagnosis)
- Initial diagnosis for maintenance planning
- Possibility for rapid intervention on structures following precise damage diagnosis
- Direct impact on safety: ability to condemn paths at risk of collapse

This solution would be very useful for structural engineers, offering access to new data currently unavailable, while improving the reliability of diagnoses: core samples and archive plans are less accurate, radiography is too complex to implement and does not detect reinforcement. For some participants, however, the added value of the technology needs to be clarified.

Maintenance engineers believe that this technology could be interesting for sensitive dams, aqueducts, levees, and hydraulic structures (SOH); also for riverbanks and canals, though it would take too much time.

According to both groups, the most relevant approach is a one-time analysis of structures, where a maximum of data would be collected to create maintenance plans. Localized inspection of parts of the structure where instability is suspected is also possible.

It is expected that the technology should be able to identify the following:

- Detection of cavities and flow zones in embankments or wing walls and stability analysis
- Density levels on dam walls
- Verification of dam plans, internal wall structure analysis
- Identification of sealed galleries in reservoir dams
- Waterproofing
- Ability to finely identify different material layers.

An inspection capacity of up to 10m depth would be desirable for dams.

For several participants, the technology is not relevant if it cannot carry out underwater inspections, and the time required to perform the diagnosis is too long. However, the technology seems interesting to participants for developing maintenance plans. The diagnosis of the entire network should be carried out in one go, with the possibility that government services could request the same level of precision for all structures if they know that some diagnostics have been done.

Maintenance engineers believe that this technology would help improve the reliability of locks, dams, and inland navigation. It is useful to have data on the structure of locks before their downtime so that work

schedules can be anticipated during these periods. Therefore, being able to regularly scan the structures is valuable.

The following challenges were identified by participants:

- A one-week inspection time for a structure seems lengthy
- Portability challenge: ensuring that the SIR system is easily movable. How to move the frame simply, possibly carried by two people (avoiding the need for a mini-crane or a rail)? Could an automated robot or underwater drones be used?
- Ability to inspect structures in water: can we avoid mobilizing divers for underwater inspections with the SIR technology?
- Potential radar deterioration due to saltwater at some sites

To encourage technology adoption, participants suggest outsourcing data processing and analysis. The scanner's sensitivity should be adjusted depending on whether dams or locks are being inspected. Participants propose further pilots on locks, manual dams, and concrete or masonry tunnels within VNF's scope.

It would be relevant to consult with INRAE (National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food, and the Environment), experts involved in developing inspection techniques, IMGC (Mediterranean Institute for Disaster Management), and CEREMA (Center for Studies and Expertise on Risks, the Environment, Mobility, and Planning) to assess the relevance of these technologies and develop best practices and recommendations.

Based on the initial ambition of the project, it was recommended that the Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR) technology be evaluated in collaboration with diagnostic prescribers, infrastructure engineers, and professional inspection bodies, to better assess its practical value in real maintenance and design contexts.

This was partially addressed during the third Living Lab in April 2025, which included maintenance experts from VNF. The exchanges confirmed that the SIR system holds potential for improving preventive maintenance but also raised concerns about the need for expert interpretation of the data, the current lack of layered material differentiation, and the complexity of integrating the system into existing operational processes.

Further engagement with engineering consultancies and asset managers is still recommended to assess how the SIR data can be translated into actionable insights. Detailed case studies demonstrating the added value of the technology in real inspection scenarios, especially where early detection enabled preventive intervention, would help support its adoption.

e) **Synchromodal Corridor Management System (SCMS)**

Freight professionals considered that this technology allowing for the collection of maximum data could enhance trust in inland waterways transport, its attractiveness and resilience. They compared it to systems dedicated to Heavy Goods Vehicles (HGVs), which are considered very reliable for tracking goods. They suggested that a similar level of reliability on inland waterways would boost competitiveness. Being informed about malfunctions in advance can also help slow down convoys, saving fuel.

Participants mentioned the Dutch PC Navigo technology, which is quite similar to SCMS and offers data for all of Europe, including alternative routes, transport times, weather, currents, etc. They suggest integrating SCMS features into this technology or into EuRIS (by adding a module) rather than developing a separate technology.

For leisure boating professionals, the alert system is unanimously considered the most useful feature. They related it to the NAVIBAT software, emphasizing the importance of having a reliable and operational alert system that removes alerts once they are no longer relevant. A question was raised about how the alerts would be received, such as through notifications on the platform. Evaluating the impact of malfunctions seems essential to provide precise reports on issues to users.

The functionalities were ranked in order of priority: the alert system, evaluating the scope of malfunctions, and the observatory. Some freight professionals, however, had doubts about the necessity of the multimodal rerouting tool, as its economic model still needs to be demonstrated.

The data that would be useful for the Freight professionals includes the location of alerts, duration, waterways, availability percentages of infrastructure, operational indicators, and a database of structures. Other useful data would include feedback from users regarding infrastructure conditions and malfunctions, as well as information about problem resolution timelines from VNF. This information could accelerate the resolution of issues hindering navigation. Information on waiting times at locks (traffic + passage) was considered to be useful to be incorporated into SCMS.

A key challenge identified by participants is harmonizing the system with other organizations (e.g., ports, SNCF, National Society of French Railways). It is desired that the interfacing systems be open rather than locked into a single solution, and capable of handling all types of data. Integrating SCMS with TMS (a Freight group participant expressed interest in collaborating with VNF and/or Cristal on SCMS) would be beneficial. It is important to test the information system interfaces between SCMS and TMS during the software design phase, with data anonymization. Participants are more cautious regarding multimodality and need additional data about its operation and economic model. They find it difficult to integrate data from other transport modes while maintaining relevance for the inland waterways: once it is rerouted to other modes (trains, trucks), it is difficult to return to inland waterways.

Real-time modal shift to rail is considered as complex, as slots must be reserved well in advance. Furthermore, real-time information still faces challenges, such as the lack of interfaces for transshipment to trucks or quick access to a handling dock.

f) **Acoustic Emissions**

The main advantages identified for this technology were as follows:

- Enabling preventive or regular maintenance
- Diagnosis with lightweight means, if calibration is appropriate
- Ability to detect invisible anomalies
- Early detection of faults, anticipating what can be heard by technicians
- Improved work scheduling and maintenance planning

- Continuous monitoring reducing daily maintenance efforts and maintaining a good level of knowledge of the infrastructure
- Periodic monitoring of hydraulic and mechanical components
- Underwater detection
- Minimizing the impact of malfunctions on users

A one-time, periodic, or continuous use of sensors seems possible. For maintenance engineers, the use of this technology would be more interesting in a continuous manner rather than intermittent, to benefit from continuous monitoring that does not require human intervention. The continuous presence of sensors would need to be assessed based on the specific challenges of the structures, risk levels, and frequency of use. Sensors could be continuously deployed on bridge cables and dams, hydraulic cylinders and hydraulic stations, with prior identification of critical points to place the sensors. Participants expressed interest in more precise data on the ability of acoustic emission sensors to detect structural deformations. This feature would indeed enhance their usefulness for monitoring structures.

Although the technology is low-cost, structural engineers believe that the entire network could be equipped, with the possibility of a flexible deployment: either equipping only the most strategic structures, or equipping all structures with fewer, less sensitive sensors on less critical ones. For maintenance engineers, equipping all structures would likely be too expensive, so selecting specific ones, possibly the most sensitive or the largest ones, where service level issues are significant, would be a better approach.

Essential technical characteristics identified include impermeability (for submerged gates), durability, reliability, low cost, and calibration suited to the specific data needed to identify malfunctions.

The sensors should be configured to detect leaks, corrosion, malfunctions in mechanical components, and ongoing deformations of operating and lifting components. For older structures with minor leaks that do not affect their operation, the alert threshold should be adjusted to differentiate between significant malfunctions. The sensors should support the localisation of malfunctions, and to recognize their nature through AE: especially differentiating between a leak noise and corrosion.

AE does not seem capable of providing the information to establish maintenance plans, as the solution is rather curative. The solution should not replace VNF technicians but offer complementary expertise and be reliable.

Several challenges were identified:

- Lack of visibility on the setup costs of the technology. Although sensor costs are low, the main expenses would be related to deployment: installation, configuration, maintenance, and data interpretation.
- High risk of noise interference, making it difficult to identify and differentiate sounds in a meaningful way.
- Sensitivity adjustments: if many sensors trigger alerts due to the aging of some older structures, the technology may not be efficient. It is also important to differentiate the data from ambient noise and ensure a relevant digital interpretation of the transmitted data to provide a clear signal to maintenance operators.

- Installing sensors at the bottom of a lock to detect leaks seems complex.
- Pre-identification is useful for predictive maintenance, but participants questioned the resources needed to act on all the potential malfunctions signalled by sensors, given the network's age.
- It is important to ensure no impact on species sensitive to ultrasound, such as bats, and to prevent acoustic interference with nearby user equipment (remote controls).

For the solution to be easily adopted, it should be reliable, low-cost, and not require VNF engineers to handle the data, with alerts automatically transmitted and intuitively understandable. Staff training would also be useful. For new structures, sensors installation could be considered at the design stage. Participants expect proof of the technology's reliability and data interpretation across various types of structures and materials.

g) Digital Twin

The main applications of digital twins identified by the structural engineers of VNF were:

- Hydraulic management: VNF already has many sensors, which could be integrated with a digital twin (e.g., dam data and lock water levels), allowing better management of water levels on a series of dams
- Handover of structures to operators after works, using models/digital twins
- Predictive maintenance tool and better knowledge of structures (not necessarily associated with a graphical interface)
- Modelling of catchment areas and routes
- Machine learning on data to predict/anticipate

The digital twin could offer advantages for flood management, low-water conditions, and provide a real-time, global view. However, participants still find this concept somewhat abstract and would like to see concrete applications.

Using a digital twin could lead to greater responsiveness and reduced maintenance costs: currently, the detailed knowledge of structures is held by personnel, but if this knowledge were computerized, each engineer could maintain more structures. However, more time would be needed to process and interpret digital twin data.

However, some maintenance engineers wonder what the DT adds to the data compared to what is directly transmitted by a sensor.

The digital twin could be associated with acoustic emission sensors: it is relevant to feed it real-time data from sensors that acquire data at regular intervals. It would also be interesting to integrate existing sensors for hydraulic management and other types such as level, pressure, biometer, and piezometer sensors. A simplified tablet interface would be preferred.

Participants suggest equipping the entire network for hydraulic management or defining perimeters for management groups.

The following challenges were identified:

- Calibration of field measurement instruments, sensor validation
- Identification, collection, and validation of relevant data
- Lack of a historical database that would allow for predictions
- Complexity of creating a digital model of the entire network with a graphical interface
- Ensuring alignment between security protocols and access rights across departments, despite the robust security architecture already in place (e.g. dedicated authentication server, secure REST endpoints, and access-controlled databases).
- It seems impossible to model all the locks, so a portion of the network should be selected, perhaps equipping neglected structures that are poorly monitored.

Participants believe it would be useful to develop a digital twin without a graphical representation of locks. Simultaneously building a BIM (Building Information Modeling) could slow development, even though the term "digital twin" suggests a 3D image.

The implementation of this technology could be part of a broader approach to developing computer-aided maintenance within the organization, which would require significant transformation. Maintenance engineers would like more concrete examples of how the DT could be implemented.

Enable stakeholders to embrace these technologies

The workshops helped identify the adoption modalities and business models of most of the technologies. For Fluv'IOTe and Smart buoys, the data were collected during interviews with VNF developing the technology.

a) CEDRE

According to the participants, the CEDRE interface should be common to both waterways and port operators. This would therefore require coordination of the governance of ports and waterways. It should also be interoperable with the data transmission systems of transporters (TMS) to promote time savings, which implies establishing connections with the managers of major TMS during the application's design. For Inland waterway carriers, although, the integration to the TMS is expensive. For the participants, two distinct interfaces should be implemented: one for the industrial fleet and another for the artisanal fleet.

The benefits of collective use of the application would be manifold for inland waterway carriers and shippers. The sharing of anonymized data on recurring routes should enable the launch of new routes, thus creating new sources of income for transporters and being a driver for modal shift.

It was referred to AI Cargo, an association funded by the PIA and Energy Savings Certificates, which develops applications similar to those that could process transporter data collected by CEDRE.

b) Fluv'IOTe

The cost of the technology is moderate, and it is developed internationally.

It would be interesting to link this data to CEDRE system. CEDRE could link the geolocation data of the barges with the loading data. Some freight operators like Cemex and CFT have started geolocating their barges, although the data is not exhaustive. They could transmit the geolocation data of their barges to VNF, which would then forward it to CEDRE and EuRIS.

There is a regulatory difficulty: for VNF to locate an object such as a barge, it would need an MMSI identifier, but barges do not have one. A temporary MMSI identifier is assigned to them while stationary, and it is then removed when the barge is in motion.

There is no information on the geolocation of the barges when they are not stationary, which is a gap in the regulations (VNF is not authorized to locate all vessels on its network).

Push boats are geolocated, as they are required to be equipped with AIS systems. It would be possible to assign a registration number to the barges; currently, on a 28m convoy, the AIS only identifies the push boat. This is problematic for navigation management and vessel loading areas. The push boat could also adjust the dimensions of its convoy in the AIS.

c) **French Smart Buoys**

This smart buoy technology is already used in maritime contexts but not in inland waterways, where additional precision is required.

The technology can work in inland waterways, but the GNSS positioning system tested is not precise enough, as the model was not designed for this function. VNF may consider collaborating with a service provider to design a custom model tailored to its needs, incorporating an alternative electronic board equipped with a multi-satellite positioning system.

It could be extended to the Moselle, Seine, and Loire rivers, which are equipped with buoys marking the channels.

d) **SIR Technology**

The professionals suggested that several scenarios could be considered. VNF could acquire radars suitable for different types of structures, provided their portability is ensured. The procurement could also be outsourced to diagnostic and inspection consulting firms. In both cases, data processing and analysis would be outsourced. The identified benefits include reducing the number of underwater inspections, lowering additional work related to inaccurate diagnostics during the preliminary design phase of maintenance works (AVP), improving structural safety, and detecting failures early to avoid network blockages.

Maintenance engineers think the service should be outsourced or managed by a dedicated national team with the necessary specialized skills.

e) **Synchromodal Corridor Management System (SCMS)**

The participants cited several existing applications similar to the SCMS, such as EuRIS and PC Navigo. The development of this application would thus occur in a highly competitive landscape. PC Navigo is a software that costs 200 euros, while EuRIS is a platform resulting from the CEF RIS COMEX project, which involves thirteen European countries, and now integrates national information and services. An EU framework directive established the main standards for cross-border River Information Systems (RIS) as early as 2005. VNF developed its own application, Navi, which provides information on navigation conditions, the status of the river network, and route options.

The SCMS should enable the modelling of the impacts of a structure malfunction on the entire connected network, with a real-time alert system, which distinguishes it from other software. Some participants believe that the SCMS should not be developed as a separate technological solution but should integrate into an existing application by offering new features. As with CEDRE, interfacing with TMS and the systems managed by Haropa and SNCF seems important, implying coordination with key transporters and operators.

By enabling transporters to anticipate malfunctions, the SCMS helps reduce costs related to transport disruptions and the successive competitiveness deficits caused by delivery delays. Charterers can benefit from the SCMS through more reliable and cost-effective transportation, with the increased reliability of river traffic enhancing its modal share. According to the participants, increasing the competitiveness of river freight would involve tracking goods on barges, similar to the current tracking of trucks. Information on the resolution time for issues by VNF would also represent significant value for the participants.

f) **Acoustic Emissions**

The use of off-the-shelf sensors seems feasible for the professionals. According to participants, the configuration of their sensitivity applied to different types of structures and materials should be outsourced by VNF, as well as the processing and interpretation of data, which should be linked to an automatic alert system that is easily understandable by maintenance engineers. Cost estimates for the equipment, installation, configuration, data interpretation, and sensor maintenance need to be clarified. Potential benefits include reduced diagnostic costs, early detection of faults to prevent network blockages, and improved structural safety.

For successful adoption, the tool must be simple and quick to use, and professionals should receive adequate training. Engineers would like to know about the cost of the technology and whether sensor replacements require external intervention or can be handled internally.

g) **Digital Twin**

Internal or outsourced data processing of the digital twin seems feasible. Participants associate the implementation of the digital twin with a broader approach to developing computer-aided maintenance at the institutional level. Harmonizing the currently different IT interfaces between territorial departments with the digital twin was also mentioned. The digital twin is therefore seen as a major driver of transformation in the institution's practices. It is likely that a hybrid model will emerge, combining

external expertise with the development of new internal skills. The potential benefits in hydraulic management include optimizing flood and low-water management, which would improve navigability and the attractiveness of the waterway. If applied to the knowledge of structures, the technology could also lead to improved maintenance efficiency.

Achievement of the KPIs by the technologies

The deliverables D6.1 and D8.1 defined KPIs to evaluate the impact of the CRISTAL technologies on the objectives of the project: modernisation of the maintenance practices, improvement of inland waterways transport resilience, and growth of modal shift.

The potential impacts of the seven technologies on these KPIs according to the assessment of the inland waterways' professionals during the living labs and interviews is shown below

Table 18 Impact on KPIs of the French pilot technologies

KPI	Measuring data	Impact of the technology							
		CEDRE	Fluv'IOTe	Smart buoys	SIR	SCMS	AE	DT	
Infrastructures. Objective : improve IWT reliability by 80%									
8.1	Availability rate of the network on the wide gauge	Average availability rate (in %) on the wide gauge	Low	Low	High	High	Low	High	Low
8.1	Reliability of the infrastructure	Proportion of preventive maintenance (avoidance of failure) compared to corrective maintenance (failure repair)	Low	Low	Low	High	Low	High	High
6.1	Capacity level during extreme weather events	Reliability of structures : number of breakdowns/structures/year	Low	Low	Low	High	Low	High	High
6.1	Early warning systems for extreme weather	Extreme weather incidents detected / month	Low	Low	High	Low	High	Low	Medium
6.1	Capacity levels during disruptions	Availability rate (in %) on the wide gauge during disruptions	Low	Low	High	Low	Medium	High	Medium
6.1	Real-time infrastructure and water level monitoring	% of network covered	Low	High	High	Medium	High	High	Medium
8.1	Modernisation of the Hydraulic Management	Rate of hydraulic infrastructure equipped with sensors	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	High	High
6.1	Real-time vessels monitoring	Tracked vs total shipments	High	Medium	Low	Low	Medium	Low	Medium
Traffic. Objective : improve IWT modal share by 20%									
6.1	Overall corridor transit time	Evolution of transit time, minutes/km	Medium	Medium	High	Medium	High	Medium	Medium
8.1	Modal shift of freight transport on IWT	Number of tons transported on the network	Medium	Medium	Low	Medium	High	Medium	Medium
8.1		Number of Twenty-Foot Equivalent Unit (TEU) transported	Medium	Medium	Low	Medium	High	Medium	Medium
8.1		Number of new projects creating a new traffics on IWW	Medium	Low	Medium	Medium	High	Medium	Medium
6.1		Additional tonne-kilometres (Tk) generated by the Modal Shift	Medium	Medium	Low	Medium	High	Medium	Medium
8.2		Average GHG emission per tonne kilometre in global freight transport	Medium	Medium	Low	Medium	High	Medium	Medium
8.2	Automation and simplification of freight transport declarations	Rate of companies TMS linked to CEDRE	High	Medium	Low	Low	Medium	Low	Medium
8.2	Improved knowledge of quays availability	Quay occupancy monitoring rates	Medium	High	Low	Low	Medium	Low	Low
6.1	Synchromodal mobility during service continuity problem (flood, damage, line interruption)	% of modal shift during line interruption	Low	Low	Low	Low	High	Low	Medium
6.1		Availability rate of multimodal transport information	Low	Low	Low	Low	High	Low	Medium

The impact levels ("Low", "Medium", "High") assigned to each KPI were derived from the performance of each technology as observed in the pilot tests, and from the qualitative feedback gathered during the living labs and interviews with inland waterway professionals. Below is a summary of the rationale by technology:

- CEDRE was rated High for automation of freight declarations (8.2) due to successful integration with CFT’s TMS and API functionality. It received mostly Low scores on infrastructure-related KPIs, as it does not contribute directly to physical infrastructure or operational monitoring. Its Medium rating on modal shift KPIs reflects its indirect potential to simplify processes and encourage adoption of IWT.
- Fluv’IOTe was rated High for improved knowledge of quay occupancy (8.2), and Medium for several resilience-related KPIs. Its combination of AIS and image-based prediction tools showed ~85% accuracy in detecting barge events, although full-scale deployment still depends on AIS data quality and generalisation

- Smart Buoys received High ratings on KPIs linked to capacity and early warning during extreme events (6.1, 6.1.1, 6.1.2), thanks to their real-time water level measurement capability. However, Low ratings were given for operational readiness due to issues with energy autonomy and data transmission reliability.
- SIR (Subsurface Inspection Radar) was rated High on KPIs related to infrastructure reliability and resilience (8.1, 8.1.1), as it supports predictive maintenance through subsurface diagnostics. However, lack of data interpretation capacity limited its use in decision-making (KPI 6.2).
- SCMS received High ratings on KPIs for real-time multimodal coordination (6.1.1, 6.1.2, 6.1.3), as it enables alert integration and rerouting through corridor management. Its Medium ratings in modal shift reflect its indirect but enabling role in improving logistics reliability.
- AE (Acoustic Emissions) received High ratings in KPIs related to condition monitoring and maintenance prediction (8.1, 8.1.1), based on its ability to detect microcracks and abnormal operations in lock gates. However, it was rated Medium in real-time coverage and data exploitation due to the need for manual data collection and interpretation.
- Digital Twin (DT) was assigned Medium ratings where it plays a future-facing, integrative role (particularly for 6.1.2 and 6.1.3). It remains under development and is not yet fully populated with live or historical data, limiting its current contribution to most KPIs.

5. Conclusions

The tests conducted on the French pilot demonstrated the potential of these technologies and the complementary nature of their impacts in promoting modal shift toward inland waterway transport and enhancing its resilience.

The development and testing of the CEDRE technology successfully engaged the interest of transport professionals. Two major operators in France have chosen to connect their Transport Management Systems (TMS) to VNF's voyage application, thereby enabling the automatic and digital transmission of valuable data on freight flows to VNF. VNF aims to extend this initiative to other key inland waterway operators and encourage the exchange of ERINOT-format data with ports such as Haropa, with the goal of enabling a unified declaration system.

The Fluv'IOTe test demonstrated, at a small scale, the feasibility of detecting barge presence along quays using an AI system combined with cameras. However, the full IT solution still needs to be developed.

VNF has confirmed its interest in an interactive buoy localization system designed to minimize channel interruptions during flood events. Scaling up the solution tested on rivers managed by VNF would require selecting the most appropriate GNSS device, balancing accuracy, signal frequency, and energy efficiency.

The tests conducted on the SIR technology demonstrated its ability to detect anomalies within lock walls, enabling proactive maintenance planning and helping to prevent lock malfunctions. Data processing work is ongoing to allow the system to differentiate between various material layers.

Inland waterway professionals have shown strong interest in several features of the Synchronodal Corridor Management System, particularly the alert mechanisms and navigation observatory. Predictive functionalities, such as estimating the duration of alerts and forecasting the impact of broken locks on port congestion, are still under development in coordination with the Digital Twin, while the observatory itself has yet to be fully structured.

The acoustic emission sensor technology, offering a rapid and cost-effective diagnosis of lock conditions, was well-received by VNF engineers. Tests showed the system's ability to detect and localize micro-cracks by comparing sound waves characteristic of normal operation with those indicating potential failures. More data needs to be collected to enable predictions.

The Digital Twins (DTs) have been developed using data from multiple pilot sites. Two types of DTs were modelled at the French pilot site:

A DT Lock, providing a smart monitoring GUI that visually represents a lock and related operational data. This DT is currently integrating data from acoustic emission sensors and, in the future, from the SIR system. It can interface with EURIS to receive real-time data on navigability status and generate alerts on lock conditions.

A DT Buoy, which displays buoy location data in a smart monitoring interface and provides an alert system related to buoy positions.

Predictive data is not yet available, however. In general, developing predictive features within DTs requires the aggregation of accurate, long-term historical data; something difficult to achieve within the constraints of a time-limited project.

Through the living labs, technology tests, and the discussions that followed, VNF professionals assessed the potential benefits of these technologies and recognized their potential value in improving day-to-day maintenance and traffic management practices.

The main barrier to the development of those technologies are:

- the difficulty to gather reliable data in IWT context, as IWW infrastructure is currently poorly digitalized
- the necessity to reskill and reorganise IWW sector in order to digitalize the infrastructure and the logistic processes. The transformation is important and obstacle due to the reluctance of change are and will occur.

Further steps are still needed for the deployment and integration of these technologies across the French and European inland waterway networks, which could be pursued through future European projects.

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